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Multi omics approaches for precision medicine

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DECLARATION

I certify that this work is original in its entirety and has not been submitted previously for any form of assessment.

Dr Lewis Francis and Dr David James helped me designing the project, the scripts and the schema for the database. Scripts, queries, their presentation, and written work presented are all my work unless otherwise stated.

SignedBeatrix Banka.....

Abstract

Introduction Cancer is the leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for nearly 10 million fatalities in 2020. Ovarian cancer, is the deadliest form of gynaecological malignancy, with around 225,500 new cases diagnosed annually and 140,200 patients losing their life. The extension of Hallmarks of Cancer with further hallmarks, such as unlocking phenotypic plasticity highlights the importance of New Generation Sequencing (NGS) for understanding better the relationship between genes and cancer subtypes. NGS generates large and often changing datasets that are difficult to store, organise and interpret, thus a flexible database is required to allow fast and easy interaction with the datasets.

Methodology To store metadata of gene counts and its BAM and FASTQ files along with the gene count tables, meta data and results of differential analysis and metadata of ChIP-sequencing along with its BAM and FASTQ files and peak count tables, MongoDB has been identified as a potential database. Using Node.js allows faster interactions with the database and MongoDB Query Language can be used to perform simple queries.

Results A database have been developed in MongoDB which stores the required datasets in an organised way. Scripts have been written to speed up the putting data into the database and to perform complex queries. Queries have been written using MQL to access data stored in the database. The database and the queries/scripts are functioning thus biological questions can be answered.

Discussion Due to its high flexibility, the database is easily can be expanded and new datasets. The database can be used to understand drugs' mechanism of action in different cancer subtypes and to identify which genes could be responsible for developing resistance. The database could be used to design subtype specific treatments, and after further development it can be available for medical professionals providing a more accessible personalised medicine approach.

Keywords: ovarian cancer, New Generation Sequencing, RNA-sequencing, ChIP-sequencing, MongoDB

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1. Introduction

1.1. Cancer

Cancer is the leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for nearly 10 million fatalities in 2020 (1). In 2019, in the United Kingdom, 28% of all deaths were caused by a form of the disease (2-4). Cancer also has the most significant economic impact of any death caused on the planet. According to an analysis authored by Dr Rijo John and Dr Hana Ross of the American Cancer Society, cancer also has the highest economic burden of all causes of death in terms of premature death and disability (5).

Cancer-related lost years of life and productivity are the single most considerable drain on the global economy compared to other causes (5). In 2008, the global economic cost of cancer-related premature death and disability was \$895 billion (5). This amount is equivalent to 1.5 per cent of the global gross domestic product (GDP). The cost of cancer is about 19 per cent greater than the cost of heart disease, which is the second most significant cause of economic loss (\$895 billion against \$753 billion, respectively). However, this analysis lacks direct medical costs, which would have increased the total economic cost of cancer (5).

The term "cancer" is a broad one, encompassing a condition that occurs when biological alterations in cells and tissues result in unregulated growth/proliferation and division (6). The Hallmarks of Cancer were proposed by Professor Hanahan and Weinberg as a set of functional skills acquired by human cells as they progress from normality to neoplastic development stages, including abilities that are critical for the formation of malignant tumours. The hallmarks can provide a useful framework which helps understanding tumour pathogenesis. In the early 2000s, the framework was consisted of only six markers: resisting apoptosis, sustaining proliferative signalling, activating invasion and metastasis, evading growth suppressors, enabling replicative immortality, and inducing angiogenesis (7). These hallmarks provided a detailed description of how malignant tumour cells able to grow, proliferate, become immortal, ensure efficient blood flow and spread to the surrounding tissues or distant parts of the body.

Later on, further hallmarks were added: avoiding immune destruction, tumour promoting inflammation, genome instability and mutation and dysregulating cellular energetics (8), as shown on figure 1. These hallmarks help understanding better the systematic effects of malignant tumour cells (inflammation), their unique way of metabolism, the mutations and why the immune system fails to destroy them. As shown in figure 1, in a 2022, a further four markers have been discussed: senescent cells, unlocking phenotypic plasticity, nonmutational epigenetic reprogramming and polymorphic microbiomes (9).

Figure 1 **The Hallmarks of Cancer**. The inner circle represents the original 6 hallmarks, the middle circle the hallmarks after the update in 2011 and the outer circle the newest, 2022 update.

Unlocking phenotypic plasticity

The development, determination, and organization of cells into tissues in order to perform homeostatic tasks during organogenesis is accompanied by terminal differentiation, in which progenitor cells stop growing upon completion of these processes. As a result, the ultimate outcome of cellular differentiation is typically antiproliferative, posing an obvious barrier to the continuous proliferation required for neoplasia. Unlocking the typically restricted potential for phenotypic plasticity in order to avoid or escape from the stage of terminal differentiation is a critical component of cancer etiology (10). Cancer cells that have dedifferentiated back to

progenitor-like cell states after starting from a normal cell that has proceeded down a route nearing or attaining a fully differentiated state may reverse their trajectory. Neoplastic cells derived from a progenitor cell that is supposed to follow a pathway leading to end-stage differentiation, on the other hand, may short-circuit the process, keeping the cancer cells spreading in a partly differentiated, progenitor-like condition. Transdifferentiation, in which cells that were previously committed to one differentiation route convert to an altogether different developmental program, acquiring tissue-specific features that were not predetermined by their normal cells-of-origin, may also occur. Notably, the loss of both of these "difference suppressors" and subsequent dedifferentiation is linked to the development of other hallmark capabilities, as are other hallmark-inducing regulators, complicating the strict characterization of this temporary hallmark as distinct and independent.

Inhibiting differentiation factor expression can aid tumorigenesis by allowing more well-differentiated cells to dedifferentiate into progenitors; however, in some cases, incompletely differentiated progenitor cells can experience regulatory changes that actively block their continued progression into fully differentiated, typically nonproliferative states. "circumvented differentiation," in which partially or undifferentiated progenitor/ stem cells exit the cell cycle and become dormant, residing in protective niches, with the potential to restart proliferative expansion (11), however under selective pressure to disrupt their programmed differentiation in some way. In addition, tissue metaplasia occurs when cells with a specific defined phenotype undergo a substantial change in morphology to become easily identifiable as parts of another tissue.

Single-cell RNA sequencing has shown highly dynamic and diverse interconversion across these subtypes, as well as unique alterations throughout lung carcinogenesis, subsequent malignant development, and therapeutic responses (12-14). As a result, rather than a simple conceptualization of a pure clonal switch from one lineage to another, these studies paint a much more complex picture of dynamically interconverting subpopulations of cancer cells exhibiting characteristics of multiple developmental lineages and stages of differentiation, a sobering realization in terms of lineage-based therapeutic targeting of human lung cancer. This dynamic phenotypic plasticity's regulatory factors are being found (14, 15, 16). As a result, these three phenotypic plasticity subclasses—dedifferentiation of mature cells back to progenitor states, blocked differentiation to freeze developing cells in progenitor/stem cell states, and transdifferentiation to alternative cell lineages—appear to be active in multiple

cancer types during primary tumour formation, malignant progression, and/or response to therapy.

The following must be considered: first, dedifferentiation and inhibited differentiation are likely inseparable in many tumour forms when the cell-of-origin—differentiated cell or progenitor/stem cell—is unknown or alternatively engaged. Second, the acquisition or maintenance of progenitor cell phenotypes and loss of differentiated features is often an imprecise reflection of the normal developmental stage, as the cancer cell is immersed in a milieu of other hallmark-enabling changes that are not present in naturally developing cells. Furthermore, another type of phenotypic plasticity is cell senescence, which is discussed in further detail below, in which cancer cells that are forced to enter presumably irreversible senescence are able to escape and resume proliferative growth (17). Finally, as with other signature capacities, cellular plasticity is not a fresh innovation or aberration of cancer cells, but rather the corruption of latent yet activatable capabilities that varied normal cells utilize to maintain homeostasis, repair, and regeneration (18).

1.2. Ovarian cancer

Ovarian cancer, is the deadliest form of gynaecological malignancy, with around 225,500 new cases diagnosed annually and 140,200 patients losing their life (19). Globally, ovarian cancer represents the 7th most common form of cancer, and among women, it is the 8th leading cause of cancer-related deaths (20-21), as depicted in Figure 3. Furthermore, among all gynaecologic malignancies in developed countries, ovarian cancer is the deadliest as its case-to-fatality is nearly three times higher than that of breast cancer. However, unlike many other solid tumours, whereas the survival rates significantly improved in the last half-century, the survival rate for ovarian cancer had remained the same since the 1980s (22). Currently, the 5-year survival rate for the disease is approximately 47% (23).

Figure 2 (A) The rates of 5-year survival with gynaecological cancer. Statistical data for ovarian cancer apply for survival rates after debulking surgery has been successfully performed. (B) Ovarian cancer is causing the most deaths among gynaecological cancers (www.cancer.net)

Symptoms and signs of ovarian cancer may include discomfort in the pelvic area, fatigue, back pain, changes in bowel habits (such as constipation), increased frequency of urinating, weight loss, abdominal bloating or swelling and quickly feeling full when eating (24).

1.2.2. Types of ovarian cancer

Ovarian cancer is a nonspecific term that refers to a wide range of cancers that affect the ovary, with the ovarian carcinoma being the most frequent type, accounting for more than 95% of all occurrences (25). Epithelial, germ cell, and specialized stromal cell tumours are the three main categories of ovarian cancer, with the majority of tumours occurring due to the transformation of epithelial cells. Only around 10% of cases originate from the sex-cord-stromal tissues or germ cells for example (26). Ovarian cancers are therefore referred to as epithelial ovarian cancers (EOC) and further split into histological subtypes, that are divided into two groups, Type I and Type II tumours.

Figure 3 Different types of ovarian cancer

Depending on the origin of the cells that make up the tumours, multiple subtypes of EOC can also be distinguished in the form of serous, mucinous, clear-cell and endometrioid cancer – as summarised in Figure 4 (27). Low-grade serous, mucinous, endometrioid, and clear cell carcinomas are examples of Type I tumours, which grow more slowly and frequently have an identifiable precursor cell (27). Despite their histological similarities and terminology, high-grade and low-grade serous carcinomas of the ovary are now thought to be two separate neoplasms with distinct processes of carcinogenesis, molecular-genetic traits, and origin sites (28). While the majority of patients seen in clinics belong to one of the four major types based on their histology, there have been a few exceptions, such as malignant transitional cell (Brenner) tumours and undifferentiated carcinomas among them (28).

Type II tumours such as high-grade serous ovarian cancer (HGSOC), which accounts for over 75% of all EOCs, are characterized by high-grade, fast progressing illness. Unfortunately, there are currently no reliable methods for HGSOC early detection. As a result, the majority of women are diagnosed after the cancer has spread to other organs, most commonly the peritoneal cavity (28).

However, the absolute lifetime risk of developing ovarian cancer is only around 1.3% and known risk factors increase the risk in individuals (22,29). The exact cause of ovarian cancer is still unknown, however there are lifestyle, hormonal and genetic risk factors which are likely to contribute to the development of the disease (30).

1.2.2 Etiology of Ovarian cancer

There are multiple factors which can increase the risk of the development of ovarian cancer. The risk is increasing along with the age – ovarian cancer is most often diagnosed in older women. Starting menstruation at an early age and/ or starting menopause at a later age might increase the risk of ovarian cancer, furthermore, taking hormone replacement therapy for controlling menopause symptoms can also be a contributing factor. There is a higher risk for those women who has never been pregnant and for those too, who have a family history of ovarian cancer. In some cases, ovarian cancer caused by inherited mutant genes, such as BRCA1 and BRCA2. Furthermore, ovarian cancer might manifest itself as a comorbidity to other diseases and conditions, such as obesity or being overweight, breast cancer, endometriosis Peutz-Jeghers syndrome and Lynch syndrome.

1.2.2.1 *Lifestyle and hormone related factors*

Women who have ovulated more frequently throughout their lives have a higher risk of ovarian cancer. Those who have never had children, those who begin ovulation at a younger age, and those who reach menopause at a later age all fall under this category (25). After menopause, reproductive medicine, and obesity, hormone therapy are all risk factors (31). Hormonal birth control, tubal ligation, and breastfeeding are all risk-reducing measures (31).

1.2.2.2 *Genetic factors*

Inherited genetic risk accounts for roughly 10% of cases; women with mutations in the BRCA1 or BRCA2 genes have a 50% probability of acquiring the disease (25). Due to genetic factors, there is a substantial heritable component – those women who have a first-degree relative affected by EOC have a threefold higher risk than those who do not have affected relatives (32). In cases where more than one member of the family is affected, often found a germline

mutation in the tumour-suppressor genes BRCA1 and BRCA2 – these mutations also increase the risk of the development of breast cancer (22). BRCA1 gene mutations were responsible for 3.6% of ovarian cancers, and the germline mutations in the BRCA2 gene were accountable for 3.3% (33). Thus, 10-20% of all EOCs are caused by germline BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutations (34). Those who carry a mutation associated with the BRCA1 gene have an overall 44% higher risk of developing ovarian cancer by age 70 compared to the average population, while the risk is 27% higher for those who have a mutation in the BRCA2 gene (35). However, the mutations in the BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes only contribute to a small part of the heritable component of ovarian cancer (36). Other gene mutations – RAD1C, BRIP1 and RAD1D are also linked with the increased risk of developing ovarian cancer of 5.2%, 5.8% and 12%, respectively (37-38). Furthermore, the variations of the BARD1, CHEK2, MRE11A, RAD50, PALB2 and ATM genes are also responsible for an increase in risk for EOC development (38-39). The significance of these genes in the homologous recombination (HR)-mediated DNA repair pathway, which is known to play a significant role in the pathophysiology of HGSOC, is the common link between them. Predominantly the clear-cell and endometrioid subtypes of EOC are more common in women with Lynch syndrome who have mutations in genes involved in DNA mismatch repair (40). Peutz-Jeghers syndrome also raises the risk of developing polyps in the digestive tract as well as cancers of the breast, colon, rectum, pancreas, stomach, testicles, ovaries, lungs, and cervix.

1.3. High-grade serous ovarian cancer

HGSOC is a diverse malignancy with high relapse and metastatic rate. Despite efforts over the last three decades to improve the outlook of this highly fatal illness, HGSOC is the most common and leading cause of mortality among gynaecologic cancers, with a 10-year survival rate of only 30% (41-42). After spreading to many sites, HGSOC is often discovered at an advanced stage, resulting in a dismal prognosis, with 80% of patients relapsing despite initial responses to surgery and chemotherapy, with many patients succumbing to treatment-resistant disease (43).

1.3.1. Stages of HGSOC

The most recent FIGO staging system (2014) is based on the degree of disease spread at the time of diagnosis. The malignancy is still localized to the ovaries or fallopian tubes in stage I (44). The illness had already progressed to other pelvic organs, such as the uterus, by stage II (44). Stage III is characterized by dissemination beyond the pelvis to organs or tissues within the peritoneal cavity or to retroperitoneal lymph nodes (44). Stage IV is defined by the spread of the cancer outside the peritoneal cavity, including the lungs, and the involvement of inguinal and other extra-abdominal lymph nodes (44). The terminal stage of the disease is distinguished by malignant intestinal obstruction caused by the development of fibrous adhesions between bowel loops by metastatic tumours and, finally, mortality from causes such as concurrent infection (45).

1.3.2. Diagnosis and HGSOc

If the diagnosis of HGSOc is suspected, the patient will undergo a pelvic and rectovaginal examination and radiographic imaging such as abdominal and transvaginal ultrasonography, MRI, PET or CT (46). Complex, hyper-vascular pelvic masses and omental/peritoneal nodules are commonly seen on imaging (47). As serum CA125 levels are elevated in most of the advanced cases, blood levels of CA125 are also measured (46). Performing laparoscopic surgery to obtain a sample from the tumour for biopsy can also have a diagnostic value and helps to determine the staging of the disease (46).

1.4. New disease understanding through Functional Genomics

1.4.1. Functional Genomics

Functional genomics is a branch of molecular biology that studies gene (and protein) functions and interactions. The large amount of data generated by genomic and transcriptomic research is used in functional genomics (such as genome sequencing projects and RNA sequencing). Functional genomics is concerned with the dynamic aspects of genomic information, such as gene transcription, translation, gene expression control, and protein–protein interactions, as opposed to the static aspects of genomic information, such as DNA sequence or structures. Functional genomics studies are distinguished by their genome-wide approach to these

concerns, which often use high-throughput methodologies rather than the more traditional "gene-by-gene" approach.

The purpose of functional genomics is to learn about the functions of genes and proteins, and eventually all of the components of a genome. The term functional genomics is frequently used to refer to the many technical approaches to studying an organism's genes and proteins, including the "biochemical, cellular, and/or physiological properties of each and every gene product" (48), though some authors include nongenic elements in their definition (49). Natural genetic diversity throughout time (such as an organism's development) or place (such as its bodily regions) may also be studied in functional genomics, as may functional disruptions such as mutations. Functional genomics include both mutation and polymorphism (such as single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) studies) of the genome, as well as the assessment of molecular activity. Transcriptomics (gene expression), proteomics (protein synthesis), and metabolomics are examples of "-omics." Multiplex approaches are generally used in functional genomics to determine the amount of many or all gene products, such as mRNAs or proteins, in a biological sample.

A more targeted functional genomics method might employ sequencing as a readout of activity to examine the function of all variations of one gene and quantify the impact of mutations. These measuring modalities work together to quantify biological processes and increase our understanding of gene and protein activities and interactions. Genetic interaction mapping is a technique at DNA level. Systematic pairwise gene deletion or suppression of gene expression can be used to find genes with related functions even if they do not physically interact. The term "epistasis" refers to the fact that the effects of two separate gene knockouts may not be additive; that is, the phenotype that follows from inhibiting two genes may differ from the total of the effects of single knockouts. Proteins produced by the translation of mRNA (messenger RNA, a coded information from DNA for protein synthesis) play an important part in gene expression regulation. It is crucial to discover DNA sequences with which they interact in order to understand how they influence gene expression. Techniques for identifying DNA-protein interactions have been developed. ChIP-sequencing, CUT&RUN sequencing, and Calling Cards are examples of these. Assays have been developed to detect accessible areas of the genome. These open chromatin areas are potential regulatory domains. ATAC-seq, DNase-Seq, and FAIRE-Seq are examples of these assays.

The most effective method for studying transcription and gene expression is RNA sequencing. This is often accomplished using next-generation sequencing (50). A subset of sequenced RNAs are short RNAs, a kind of non-coding RNA molecule that plays an important role in transcriptional and post-transcriptional gene silencing, also known as RNA silencing. Next-generation sequencing is the gold standard technology for discovering, characterizing, and analyzing non-coding RNAs, a 3rd subset of epigenomic changes observed in the cancer epigenome, implicated in the etiology of disease.

1.4.2. Human and functional genomics – mutation analysis and Ovarian cancer and HGSOc

Patients with high-grade serous ovarian cancer (HGSOc) who had first debulking surgery followed by platinum-based chemotherapy, which is the standard of care for all advanced stage EOC patients; carboplatin mixed with paclitaxel is the standard of care, regardless of histotype (ref). Clinical reactions might be quite diverse. A tiny fraction of women have excellent long-term survival (LT, 10+ years), but others develop initial resistance to treatment and die in less than 2 years (short term) (ST) (54). Patients with LT survival were younger on average than those with ST (56 vs. 61 years mean age at diagnosis) and were less likely to have residual disease post-surgery (35 % versus 76 %) (54).

CA125 levels in blood serum did not related with survival at diagnosis; however, LT survivors had considerably decreased CA125 levels post-surgery and at the completion of treatment (54). However, survival was discovered to be reliant on mutation rates as well: Early investigations on breast and ovarian cancer cell lines found that cells with either mutant or hypermethylated BRCA1 were sensitive to platinum-based chemotherapy (51,55-57). The tumour with the greatest mutation load carried a pathogenic BRCA1 variation (p.Asn1236Phefs) as well as two-hit somatic MLH1 inactivation via a truncating mutation (54). Greater mutation rate has been linked to improved immunogenicity in other cancers (51,58). which might explain the increased survival in HGSOc. A somatic MLH1 mutation was also found in a long-term survivor patient in the TCGA cohort (p.Arg100Ter) (51).

Patch et al. (59) investigated methylation variations in 13 paired resistant and sensitive HGSOc and discovered 94 CpG probes with a methylation differential of more than 10% between the sensitive and resistant HGSOc, impacting COLA1A1, SPTBN4, and MYOID genes. In a study

of 20 EOC patients, hypomethylation in GREB1, TGIF, TOB1 and hypermethylation in TMC05, PTPRN, and GUCY2C was related with longer survival (60).

Hafner et al. investigated the difference in DNA methylation between pools of HGSOC DNA with poor or excellent survival, followed by confirmation in a separate group of samples, and discovered two genes, RUNX3 and CAM21, to be related with PFS (progression-free survival) (61). Increased methylation of these two genes was related with decreased gene expression in cell lines. Agents for DNA demethylation BET inhibitors, for example, have been employed to express genes repressed by DNA methylation.

BETi, such as JQ1 and I-BET, have been demonstrated to be variable effective in a variety of malignancies by inhibiting the binding of histone's acetylated lysines, displacing BET proteins from chromatin and reducing gene transcription (62-63). JQ1 inhibits the development of cisplatin-treated ovarian cancer cell lines and xenografts by suppressing BRD4-mediated ALDH1A1 expression, which is linked to chemoresistance in ovarian cancer. These examples above show the importance and the opportunities in functional genomics to understand and identify causing agents of drug resistance and those which promotes long-time survival.

1. 1.5. Functional genomic tools and databases development

1.5.1 Next Generation Sequencing analysis and Transcriptome analysis (RNA-seq)

RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) is the study of RNA using any of a next-generation sequencing methods (often known as deep sequencing due to its large coverage potential). It does not typically refer to directly sequencing RNA molecules; the sequencing procedure is the same for RNA-seq and DNA sequencing, but the library preparation and analysis are significantly different. Reverse transcription is commonly used in the production of RNA-seq libraries. In certain circumstances, the direction of the transcription is lost during strand amplification, however methods for determining transcript orientation are available. RNA-seq data processing may comprise transcript assembly, alternatively spliced transcript finding, or new transcript discovery, as well as transcript quantification. Specifically, RNA-Seq allows researchers to examine alternative gene spliced transcripts, post-transcriptional alterations, gene fusion, mutations/SNPs, and variations in gene expression over time, as well as differences in gene expression across groups or treatments (64). RNA-Seq may look at multiple

populations of RNA, such as total RNA, small RNA, such as miRNA, tRNA, and ribosomal profile, in addition to mRNA transcripts (65). Exon/intron borders may also be determined using RNA-Seq, as can previously defined 5' and 3' gene boundaries. Single cell sequencing, in situ sequencing of fixed tissue, and native RNA molecule sequencing with single-molecule real-time sequencing are examples of recent RNA-Seq breakthroughs (66). Copy number variation, microbial contamination, transposable elements, cell type (deconvolution), and the existence of neoantigens are further examples of growing RNA-Seq applications as a result of bioinformatics algorithm progress (67).

1.5.2 Chromatin Immunoprecipitation (ChIP-seq)

ChIP-sequencing, often known as ChIP-seq, is a technique for studying protein-DNA interactions. ChIP-seq combines chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) with massively parallel DNA sequencing to detect DNA-associated protein binding sites. It may be used to precisely map global binding sites for any protein of interest. ChIP-seq is largely used to study how transcription factors and other chromatin-associated proteins influence phenotype-influencing pathways. Understanding how proteins interact with DNA to control gene expression is critical to understanding various biological processes and disease states (68). This epigenetic data complements genotype and expression analyses. ChIP-seq technique is now viewed largely as a replacement for ChIP-chip, which requires a hybridization array. Chromatin immunoprecipitation can isolate specific DNA locations that are in direct physical contact with transcription factors and other proteins. ChIP generates a library of target DNA locations that have been bound to a protein of interest. To investigate the pattern of any protein's interaction with DNA, or the pattern of any epigenetic chromatin alterations, massively parallel sequence studies are employed in combination with whole-genome sequence databases. This is applicable to the set of ChIP-able proteins and modifications, which includes transcription factors, polymerases and transcriptional machinery, structural proteins, protein modifications, and DNA modifications (69). As an alternative to relying on antibodies, technologies such as DNase-Seq and FAIRE-Seq have been developed to identify the superset of all nucleosome-depleted or nucleosome-disrupted active regulatory areas in the genome (70-72).

1.5.3 Dataset production and management

Managing the massive amounts of RNA-seq data generated during studies is time-consuming and difficult. For example, the Hiseq2000 (Illumina) sequencer may generate up to 200 million 100-nt reads (about 50 GB) of data in a single lane in a single sequencer run (73). These data must be processed not just to detect matches to the transcriptome, but also must be assembled into transcripts and quantified before biological meaning can be deduced (73). Duplicate or triple experimental datasets reduce data variability and allow for improved data interpretation (73).

FASTQ files. The most common data format for storing read data is FASTQ. This format includes an ID number for each read, the read sequence, and a quality score for each read. A FASTQ file is a text file that contains the sequence data from flow cell clusters that pass filter. If samples were multiplexed, the first step in creating a FASTQ file is demultiplexing. Demultiplexing allocates clusters to samples depending on the index sequence of the clusters. The completed sequences are written to FASTQ files per sample after demultiplexing. If samples were not multiplexed, the demultiplexing stage is skipped, and all clusters are given to a single sample for each flow cell lane. One Read 1 (R1) FASTQ file is prepared for each sample per flow cell lane during a single-read run. For a paired-end run, one R1 and one R2 FASTQ file are generated for each sample and lane. FASTQ files are compressed and have the *.fastq.gz extension.

1.5.3.1 Databases

A database is a structured collection of data that is stored and retrieved electronically in computing. Small databases can be kept on a file system, but big databases are kept on computer clusters or in the cloud. Database design encompasses formal methodologies as well as practical factors such as data modelling, efficient data representation and storage, query languages, sensitive data security and privacy, and distributed computing challenges such as concurrent access and fault tolerance.

To gather and analyze data, a database management system (DBMS) is the software that interacts with end users, applications, and the database itself. The DBMS software also includes the essential features required to administer the database. A database system is the combination of the database, the DBMS, and the accompanying applications. The term "database" is

frequently used in a broad sense to refer to any of the DBMS, the database system, or an application linked with the database.

Database management systems may be classified by computer scientists based on the database models that they support. In the 1980s, relational databases dominated. These represent data as rows and columns in a sequence of tables, and the vast majority write and query data using SQL. Non-relational databases, sometimes known as NoSQL because they employ distinct query languages, became popular in the 2000s.

1.5.3.1.2 SQL databases

Relational databases are particularly good at storing structured data. They offer comprehensive querying layers and store data in the smallest possible footprint by de-normalizing the data. As a result of the data being denormalized, accessing it necessitates complex joins. Relational databases have been around for a long time and have been proven in a wide range of applications. There are numerous licensed and open-source relational databases available. Relational databases are typically designed to work on a single node. However, most of the popular ones have recently added cluster support through the use of Sharding, which builds redundancy into the database, so it is resilient to the loss of a node. However, because partition tolerance is built into their foundation, sharding is implemented less effectively than their multi-node NoSQL counterparts, resulting in reduced performance. In addition, Sharding raises costs and necessitates close management.

Most relational databases prioritize consistency and availability over partition tolerance, meaning that relational databases are not very good at handling large amounts of data because they must be stored in a single system or require constant maintenance due to their limitations in multi-node operation.

1.5.3.1.3. NoSQL databases

On the other hand, NoSQL databases are ideal for storing semi-structured or unstructured data because they do not enforce a specific schema for tables, meaning that data attributes can be added anytime without affecting the overall structure of the table or adding redundant elements

to the remaining rows. All NoSQL databases are either schema-free or have relaxed schemas which can be easily modified without the need to redesign the whole structure of the database, as it shown on Figure 10. Nor the data or the schema require any sort of definition and heterogenous structures are allowed too. They do not require data normalization or object-relational mapping. Furthermore, NoSQL databases works much faster than relational databases due to the possibility of horizontal screening: the database load can be distributed on multiple hosts instead of only one server.

Table 1 Comparison between relational and NoSQL databases

	<i>Relational Databases</i>	<i>NoSQL Databases</i>
<i>Type</i>	Relational	Non-relational
<i>Schema flexibility</i>	Rigid, static schema based on relationships	Non-rigid and very flexible dynamic schema
<i>Language</i>	Structured Query Language (SQL)	Un-structured Query Language
<i>Data consistency</i>	enforcing	Eventful
<i>Storage storing</i>	Structured data stored in tables	Un-structured data stored in JSON
<i>Write performance requirements</i>	Safe, consistent, slower	Fast writing ability
<i>Read requirements</i>	Great ability to query data and execute complex joins	Joins are not supported, lack of ability to perform complex queries
<i>Infrastructure constraints</i>	More expensive	Cheaper

Different types of NoSQL can be distinguished based on the way they structure the data format. Key-value databases store information as a collection of key-value pairs. While they are not widely used in persistent storage, they are worth mentioning due to their widespread use in modern architectures. As caching providers, key value-based storage solutions are widely used and necessary to share data quickly across multiple services. Key-value databases are based on distributed hash tables and Amazon’s Dynamo paper. Their primary purpose is to handle massive amounts of data and store schema-free content allowing the benefit of simple data insertion and retrieval. Data are stored in hash tables with unique keys, and values can be strings

or in BLOB or JSON format. There are variations to choose from to store values in lists, strings, hashes set or use sorted sets as keys.

Figure 4 Data structure used by Redis, a Key-Value Database (<https://redis.com/redis-enterprise/data-structure/>)

Key-value databases can be used for collections, associative arrays, and dictionaries. Key-value data stores are ideal for storing session information, user profiles, product comments, and product recommendations. For example, Redis is used to manage the Twitter timeline, store lists of images, galleries, users, boards, followers, and un-followers on Pinterest, and authorize rate points and assure the rightness of the Bitcoin transactions Coinbase. Memcached is used to maintain the cache of determined and moderate databases on Quora.

Column-oriented databases store data in the form of columns and perform well when specific columns are accessed. In these databases, data rows can span multiple nodes or partitions. They work on the assumption that rows are large enough to scale across multiple nodes and that all columns are rarely accessed simultaneously. Column-oriented databases have a structure based on Google's Big Table distributed storage file system. Column-oriented databases are essentially designed to work on columns, with each column treated independently. For each column, all values are stored running simultaneously.

Figure 5 Data structure of Cassandra Apache (<https://www.researchgate.net/figure/cassandra-data-model-fig6-274174394>)

Data in column-oriented databases are stored in column-specific files of the same type. Query processors operate on columns, which improves query performance by allowing access to specific column data. It also provides performance on aggregation queries. In addition, because all data associated with a single column is of the same type, it is ideal for compression.

The column-oriented database provides a highly scalable architecture and is popular among organisations working on the internet of things, big data, and personalised content recommendations because they are fast for insertion and retrieval. Apache Cassandra is used in Spotify to store metadata about songs and artists and the parameters of user-profiles for better personalisation and on Outbrain for serving personalised content recommendations. Facebook uses HBase for search indexing in the “Nearby Friends” feature.

Document-oriented databases data is stored in a collection of documents, and each document is a collection of key-value pairs. The keys can access all values or data stored in documents, which are stored as objects in JSON form. Documents are independent units, allowing seamless mapping from the object world of programming languages to data storage. All documents are distinct from one another and are schema-free, making them adaptable and straightforward to modify.

Collections are used to store documents and groups of various types of data. Document-oriented databases benefit from documents being in a single collection do not have to have the same set of fields, and the data type for a field can vary between documents within a collection. In order to change the structure of documents in a collection, such as adding new fields,

removing existing fields, or changing field values to a different type, update the documents to the new structure. This adaptability makes it easier to map documents to entities or objects. Even if a document differs significantly from the others in the collection, it can match the data fields of the represented entity.

Figure 6 Structure of data storing in document-oriented databases (<https://docs.mongodb.com/manual/core/data-modeling-introduction/>)

Document databases are fully flexible and are recommended to use for dictionaries, associative arrays and collections. For example, Cisco uses Couchbase in order to achieve greater scalability, and SEGA uses MongoDB to manage game accounts, by Aer Lingus for managing internal applications and handling ticket management.

Graph Databases data is stored in Graph Databases as nodes and relationships. They assist users in expressing complex relationships between data elements and querying them with specialized Graph Query Languages. Graph databases are designed to store data that changes frequently and are able to represent any kind of data. In addition, it has the benefit of a high level of accessibility as it uses indexes for lookups. Each graph database comprises one or more nodes and edges – the nodes represent entities while the edges are connecting nodes to demonstrate their relationship. Each node and edge have their unique identifier and is aware of the nodes around. Starting from any arbitrary or start node, the graph can be traversed depth-first or breadth-first.

Figure 7 The structure of data in Neo4j (<https://towardsdatascience.com/presenting-multiple-node-label-support-and-graph-mutability-features-of-the-neo4j-graph-data-a0b0ea744884>)

When dealing with large datasets, graph databases are being used to establish relationships and outperform relational databases in terms of query performance, significantly as data sets grow larger. An example, Neo4j is used by Walmart to provide relevant product promotions and recommendations to its customers, by Medium to build its social network and improve content personalisation, and by Cisco to analyse customer support issues in anticipating bugs.

A Hierarchical Databases model is the first database model which IBM has created in the 1960s. In this model, the data is organized in the form of a tree. The information is stored in the form of records that are linked to one another. A record is a collection of fields, each of which has only one value. A record's type determines which fields it contains. According to the hierarchical database model, each child record can have only one parent, whereas each parent record can have one or more child records. The entire tree must be traversed to retrieve data from a hierarchical database, beginning with the root node.

Figure 8 Data structure in hierarchical databases (<https://www.smartsheet.com/relational-database-modeling>)

The best examples of hierarchical databases are Microsoft's Windows registry and IBM's IMS database.

Object-oriented Databases. An *object-oriented database* is a database management system in which data is represented as objects, as in object-oriented programming. Object-oriented databases are distinct from table-oriented relational databases. Object-relational databases are a cross between the two approaches, combining database and object-oriented programming language capabilities. Object-oriented database management systems (OODBMSs) enable object-oriented programmers to create products, store them as objects, and replicate or modify existing objects to create new objects within the OODBMS. As a result of the database being integrated with the programming language, the programmer can maintain consistency within one environment by using the same representation model for both the OODBMS and the programming language. Relational DBMS projects, on the other hand, keep a more apparent separation between the database model and the application. Some object-oriented databases are designed to work well with object-oriented programming languages like Delphi, Ruby, Python, JavaScript, Perl, Java, C#, Visual Basic.NET, C++, Objective-C, and Smalltalk; others, like JADE, have their own programming languages.

Figure 9 Model of data structuring in object-oriented databases (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Evolution-of-Object-Oriented-Database-Systems-By-Alzahrani/6d1c233393fa9064957a75043cee480ce6a36478>)

Object-oriented databases are commonly used in web-scale production and research. Some examples for object-oriented databases are NEO, JADE, db4o and Versant.

2. Thesis Hypothesis, aims and objectives

The hypothesis for the project states that ‘Developing a flexible database method is crucial in understanding the integration of transcriptomic and epigenomic data (mainly derived from CHIP seq), helping to derive scientific hypothesis and analysis of large NGS datasets toward new disease related target ID in HGSOC’.

Aims and Objectives. With the rise of NGS data that is publicly available and the affordability and ease of technology application, at both population and single cell level, more advanced informatics tools are needed to mine and query these large datasets – allowing non NGS experts such as clinicians to analyse and utilise the vast arrays of data available. This project, focusing on functional genomics in the form of transcriptomic and epigenomic data, aims to develop a flexible, multimodal database for query interrogation, enabling scientific hypothesis development. If functional, this database will enable analysed transcriptomic and epigenomic data to be included in the form of JSON files, allowing users to derive queries to understand and visualise overlap between CHIP seq derived peaks and genome locations (enhancers and gene proximal promoters) as well as lists of functional genes associated with a given gain or

loss of a peak. While limited in scope to transcriptomic and ChIP-seq data set in the case of this project dissertation, the database developed is the basis on which to develop multimodal data interrogation and visualisation efforts, supporting the research agenda of the Reproductive Biology and Gynaecological Oncology group, centred on functional genomics and the disease phenotype.

3. Methods

Given that the scope of this project was to design and demonstrate an effective database for querying of NGS datasets, the methods used were results of careful investigation. In this method sections we briefly outline the methods used to create the database, while full explanation of the decisions and processes undertaken to choose appropriate methods are given in the results section.

3.1. NGS data in the database

The following datasets were written to the database:

BAM details for both RNA-seq and ChIP-seq

The requested STAR aligner output (with the appropriate settings) is a BAM file. STAR will, by default, deliver a file in SAM format. The BAM file is a binary, compressed version of the SAM file, which is also known as the Sequence Alignment Map format. The SAM file is a tab-delimited text file containing information for each individual read and its alignment to the genome.

FASTQ details for both RNA-seq and ChIP-seq

The FASTQ format is a human-readable file format that includes nucleotide base sequences, the computed confidence for each base in a sequence, and metadata detailing the read's origin down to its position on the sequencing platform flow-cell. Most, if not all, current sequencers generate FASTQ files or data that may be easily converted to FASTQ files, and almost all bioinformatics tools dedicated to raw sequence processing accept FASTQ files as input. An

untrimmed, unfiltered FASTQ file is regarded the "raw" sequence standard in a study and should always be kept as a permanent component of the study's data.

Meta data of gene count tables

Meta data of gene reads contains the counts ID, the name of the file stores the counts, the ID of the related BAM file, the method which has been used, information about what has been counted, the date of the performance, the initials of the operator and the location of the file on the server.

Meta data of differential analysis performed between two gene count tables

Meta data of differential analysis contains the analysis ID, the name of the file stores the data of the analysis, the two gene count tables used for control and the two used as samples for the analysis as in differential analysis the gene expression of all genes are compared in two samples. For each sample at least two replicates were produced. Hence in the GeneCountsControl and GeneCountsSample fields there are two references to gene count tables. Finally, the filters column contains any filters that have been applied to the dataset after processing. For instance, in this case all genes have been filtered so the adjusted p-value is > 0.05 . For the upregulated analysis the log2foldchange must be > 0 and for the down regulated the log2foldchange must be < 0 .

Meta data of ChIP sequencing

Meta data of gene reads contains the counts ID, the name of the file stores the counts, the ID of the related BAM file, the method which has been used, information about what has been counted, the date of the performance, the initials of the operator and the location of the file on the server.

Gene count tables

The amount of reads that have been mapped to each gene may be tallied. This yields a table of counts.

The results of each differential analysis

The results of the differential analysis performed between two different gene count table.

Peak count tables

Data frame contains rows corresponding to genomic windows, columns for chromosomes, start and finish locations, and a column for sample counts.

3.2. Setting up the MongoDB database on an atlas cluster

In order to set up a database, a new cluster has been created in MongoDB Atlas. The process has started with registering, which is possible using an email address or a Google account. Unlike Google, MongoDB is not prompting two-factor verification, registering with a Google account has been chosen for better safety. Afterwards a new organization has been created, and members have been added, followed by creating a project for the organization.

Succeeding to create the first project, Atlas prompts its users to log in and deploy their first cluster. The M0, M2 and M5 are different cluster tiers to choose from when creating a cluster. The starter cluster is free, end-to-end encrypted and optimal for developing small applications. Amazon Web Services (AWS) has been chosen as a cloud provider with the recommended North Virginia region.

It was followed by selecting the M0 cluster and creating a name for the cluster. Afterwards, the cluster has been created the current IP address has to be added to enable the connection.

3.3. MongoDB shell for simple queries

The mongo shell is a JavaScript-based interactive MongoDB interface. The mongo shell can be used to query and update data, as well as conduct administrative tasks.

Before creating a database, MongoDB Shell had to be installed on the computer. For macOS, it has to be performed by using Homebrew package manager. Once the MongoDB Shell is installed, the database in the Atlas has to be connected to the MongoDB Shell by pasting and

running the connection string in the terminal. Once the password is entered correctly, the MongoDB Shell is ready to add data to the database.

While working in MongoDB Shell, a specific language, the MongoDB query language has been used, allowing easy navigation between databases and collections. The table below explains some of the commands that have been used:

Table 2 Mongo DB MQL commands and operators

Command	Function
insertOne	inserts one document to an existing collection
insertMany	inserts multiple documents into an existing collection
find	Filters within collection to find the document that matches the specified criteria
updateOne	updates the requested fields of a document that matches the specified criteria
updateMany	updates more than one document at the same time
replaceOne	fully replaces a document
aggregate	Performs aggregation tasks such as \$group using an aggregation pipeline
\$unwind	Deconstructs an array field from the input documents in order to return a document for each element. Each output document is the same as the input document, except with the array field's value replaced by the element.

\$group	The provided <code>_id</code> expression takes in documents and returns a document for each different grouping.
\$count	The number of documents in a collection or view is counted.
\$match	Filters the documents such that only those that meet the stated condition(s) are sent on to the next pipeline stage.
\$project	Only returns the requested elements/hides the elements requested i.e.: \$project: { _id: 1 } - <code>_id</code> field will be presented, \$project: { _id: 0 } - <code>_id</code> field will not be presented.
\$objectToArray	Creates an array from an object.
\$filter	Returns an array containing just the entries that satisfy the criterion.
pretty	Displays the results in an organised way.

3.4. Interacting with the database using Node.js and JavaScript

Scripts for node.js have been written in *Atom* for better readability, editability and clarity. *Node.js* has been used to perform more complicated tasks, such as inserting a full collection, containing numerous documents and to create nested fields within a document. Using Node.js made possible to connect different files using a named key and insert the documents according to their relationship to each other. All scripts have been written in JavaScript.

3.5. Atom

Atom is a free, open-source desktop program that runs on almost all operating systems (macOS, Windows, Linux). In HTML, JavaScript, and CSS, this hackable (customizable) text and source-code editor can be completely customized. In addition, syntax highlighting is available in Atom's default packages for a variety of programming languages and file formats. Atom has been used for writing and editing queries and scripts for Node.js.

As the free tier version of Atlas has some limitations in the levels of aggregation pipelines, the database has been downloaded to the local computer and the final queries have been performed there.

4. Results

4.1. Database schema

4.1.1. MongoDB overview

Data from NGS is constantly evolving and changing, thus a fixed SQL table would not be able to new types of data to be added to the database without changing the schema. A database was required which allows frequent changes, updates, easy data uploads and downloads and to store differently structured data.

Working with updated sequencing techniques, the attributes of data that will be input are often unknown. MongoDB offers very flexible document schemas, any kind of data structure can be manipulated and modelled easily. as MongoDB documents Related documents are stored together in collections. The documents store data, and collections are built up of related documents. For example, in the gene counts collection each document stores the information of the gene counts (file name, location, date, counts etc.) and another collection for differential analysis each document stores information of the analysis that were performed between two gene count tables (file name, file location, sample table, control table etc.). While in traditional SQL databases the columns of each database table must be determined and declared before inserting data, in MongoDB documents in the same collection may contain different fields. Figure x shows the different structure of the SQL and NoSQL databases. These can be modified anytime easily by adding new fields, removing existing ones, updating the documents to a new structure or change the field values to a new type. The mapping of documents to entities or objects is made easier by this flexibility.

Figure 10 Differences between the structure of relational databases (A) and NoSQL database, MongoDB (B)

Furthermore, MongoDB allows related data to be embedded in an object or array within a single document making representation of their relationship clearer. Documents can also be embedded within other documents. This benefits querying as a single database operation can be used to retrieve and manipulate related data. To access the items of an array and the fields of an embedded document, MongoDB employs the dot notation. Embedded documents, also known as nested documents, are ones that include one document inside another. For example, `RNASeq.geneCounts.bamDetails.fastqDetails` allows access to the `fastqDetails` field in `bamDetails` document in the `geneCounts` collection of the `RNASeq` database.

MongoDB represents documents in JSON format. JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a part of the JavaScript language. JSON is formed by simple associative containers, where a string key is mapped to a value (which can be a number, string, function, or even another object). Because of this fundamental language feature, JSON might be expressed in text in a fairly simple way (figure 1): using a key-value format and separating field names (keys) from their values by a colon. Groups of key value pairs are enclosed in curly braces, and are referred to as objects. Objects can be nested inside other objects. The field-value pairs are separated from each other by a comma. Arrays of data (i.e., a vector of integers or a vector of strings) are stored in square brackets. JSON is a text-based format and text parsing is very slow, it only supports a limited number of basic data types and takes up a lot of space, which reduces the efficiency of the database. To overcome these issues, MongoDB stores its data in BSON (Binary JSON), and binary version of a JSON. This allows much quicker parsing, and optimized data storing for space, flexibility, and speed. In addition, using BSON format to store data allows further data types. On the other hand, BSON is only machine-readable. Any data that can be represented in JSON can be stored in MongoDB and all data can be easily retrieved in JSON.

Figure 11 MongoDB represents the documents in JSON. Curly braces ({}) are used for objects, commas (,) are used for separating key-value pairs, and square brackets ([]) are used for arrays.

Table 2 introduces the different types of data which can be stored in JSON fields that can be used in a document:

<code>_id</code>	Holds an ObjectId. This is used as a primary key, every document must have its unique ID. Can be any type, except an array. Cannot be duplicated or muted.
String	Can contain any text as the BSON strings are UTF-8 coded. This makes it possible to store most international characters.
Timestamps	Special type for internal MongoDB use that is not associated with the Date type.
Date	Can represent the number of milliseconds and in a date range of about 290 million years into the past and future.
Numerical data	Floats and integers

Table 2 Different type of fields available in BSON and their properties

The data stored in MongoDB is relatively easy to access as it supports access from a range of computer languages. Data is accessible from languages in their native format – using Python the data will be structured in dictionaries, with Java it will be shown as maps and querying in JavaScript will get the data in associative arrays. Comma-separated values (csv), common in spreadsheet applications and are supported by MongoDB as a source for importing and exporting datasets. In addition, MongoDB has its own, fully featured query language, the MongoDB Query Language (MQL) which allows performing complex analytical pipelines and querying deep into documents to access the data needed.

4.1.1.1. RNA-seq

The original schema that was created for this project resembled an SQL style approach with foreign keys were used for linking the different collections together. A separate collection was created for the meta data of gene counts, including the BAM and fastq files, another collection for the gene count tables, one for the metadata of the differential analysis and one for the results of the differential analysis. This schema required querying and linking back to the fastq files collection every time, when meta data was required for an experiment in the BAM file, gene counts or differential analysis collection. This would be simple using join operations and foreign keys in an SQL database. However, MongoDB and MQL suggest keeping related data, which is accessed together in the same document as they do not support join operations and foreign keys. Since there is a one-to-one mapping between the metadata, fastq files, BAM files, and gene counts (i.e., there is only one gene count table for each fastq or pair of fastq files), a new collection was created where these were stored together. Storing them all in the same collection greatly simplified querying and returning data using MQL.

For the differential analysis, the results are a many to one mapping (Every differential analysis requires 2 different sample types with at least two experiments for each). Therefore, a different collection has been created containing each differential analysis together with the meta data related to them. This collection is linked back to the gene counts collection which contains the meta data and gene count tables which helps querying between the two collections.

In conclusion, instead of the original four collections, two different collections have been created that store the data together and thus querying became much simpler. The data fields for the RNA-seq metadata and differential analysis collections are shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Figure 12 The original SQL-type schema and the new, MongoDB supported schema of RNA-seq data

4.1.1.1.1. Data fields in RNA-seq geneCounts collection

It is critical to maintain account of every action performed on the data in order to compare samples without bias. MongoDB mandates that each document have a unique ID. Knowing where the data is kept is essential in order to it to be used in the future. Furthermore, it is fundamental to keep track on the lab, origin, or patient ID of the datasets in case several laboratories employ different methodologies and thus cannot be compared, or if one lab is discovered to be functioning inaccurately, so then the changes can be followed in the impacted data files.

Field	Data	Description
-------	------	-------------

Fastq files	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	File name	File name of the fastq file
	Experiment	Name of the NGS experiment from which the file originated
	Sequencing Date	Date of sequencing
	Sample	Type of sample sequenced
	Treatments	Any treatments applied to the sample
	Other	Any other information
	Replicates	A list of all replicates of the sample
	Pair-ended	Name of other pair (if pair-ended experiment)
	Sequencing facility	Sequencing provider
	Sequencing Technology	Type of sequencing
	SC or bulk	Single cell or bulk sample
	Downloaded	Location file downloaded from if publicly available data
	Operator	Person who created the NGS sample
File location	Location of file on RBGO server	
BAM files	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	File name	File name of the BAM file
	Fastq 1	ID of fastq file 1
	Fastq 2	ID of fastq file 2
	Aligner	Aligner program used to align to genome
	Aligner Version	Version of the aligner program
	Aligner Settings	Settings of the aligner
	Genome build	Genome build used for alignment
	Date	Date of alignment
	Operator	Person who performed the alignment
	File Locations	Location of BAM files on RBGO server
Gene counts	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	Counts	Gene count data
	File Name	File name of the gene count data file
	BAM files	ID of BAM file used for generating gene counts

	Method	Method for generating gene counts
	Count table type	Genomic feature of counts (genes, miRNA, lncRNA etc)
	Date	Date of gene count
	Operator	Person who performed the gene count
	File Locations	Location of gene count files on RBGO server

Table 3 Data stored in RNA-seq geneCounts collection

Data fields in RNA-seq differentialAnalysis collection

It is critical to maintain account of every action performed on the data in order to compare samples without bias. MongoDB mandates that each document have a unique ID. Knowing where the data is kept is essential in order to it to be used in the future. Furthermore, it is fundamental to keep track on the lab, origin, or patient ID of the datasets in case several laboratories employ different methodologies and thus cannot be compared, or if one lab is discovered to be functioning inaccurately, so then the changes can be followed in the impacted data files.

Field	Data	Description
Differential analysis	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	Filename	Names of file containing differential analysis results
	Gene counts control	ID's of gene count files used as the sample for differential analysis
	Gene counts sample	ID's of gene count files used as the control for differential analysis
	Filters	Any filters used when processing the data
	DysRegulation	Whether data is upregulated, downregulated or both.

Table 4 Data stored in RNA-seq differential analysis collection

ChIP-seq

Based on the schema that has been created for the RNA-sequencing data, a similar schema has been implemented for ChIP-sequencing data, using peak data rather than gene count tables. Originally, a separate collection was going to be created to include overlaps data analogous to the differential analysis collection in the RNA-sequencing model. However, it was realised that overlap type questions could be answered by simply querying the peak data, so the extra collection was eliminated, simplifying the design of the database.

Data fields in ChIPSeq collection

Field	Data	Description
Fastq files	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	Experiment	Name of the NGS experiment from which the file originated
	Fastq1	ID of fastq file 1
	Fastq2	ID of fastq file 2
	InputFastq1	ID of input fastq file 1
	InputFastq2	ID of input fastq file 2
	File location Fastq1	Location of fastq file 1 on the server
	File location Fastq2	Location of fastq file 2 on the server
	File location Input Fastq1	Location of input fastq file 1 on the server
	File location Fastq2	Location of input fastq file 2 on the server
	Sequencing Date	Date of sequencing
	Target	The target region of the gene
	Sample	Type of sample sequenced
	Condition	Condition (disease) of sample
	Input sample	Type of sample of control dataset
	Condition Input	Condition (disease) of input sample
	Treatments	Any treatments applied to the sample
Other	A list of all replicates of the sample	

	Replicates	Name of other pair (if pair-ended experiment)
	Pair-ended	Name of other pair (if pair-ended experiment)
	Sequencing facility	Sequencing provider
	Sequencing Technology	Type of sequencing
	Downloaded	Location file downloaded from if publicly available data
	Operator	Person who created the NGS sample
BAM files	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	BAM	ID of BAM file
	InputBAM	ID of input BAM file
	File location BAM	Location of BAM file on the server
	File location Input BAM	Location of input BAM file on the server
	Aligner	Aligner program used to align to genome
	Aligner Version	Version of the aligner program
	Aligner Settings	Settings of the aligner
	Preprocessing	What preparation has been done
	Genome build	Genome build used for alignment
	Date	Date of alignment
	Operator	Person who performed the alignment
Peaks	_id	Unique ID of database entry
	BAM ID	ID of BAM file
	File Name	Names of file containing peak counts
	Peak Caller	Program used for peak calling
	Peak Caller Version	Version of the peak caller program
	Peak Caller settings	Settings of the peak caller
	Count table type	The type of the output file
	Date	Date of alignment
	Operator	Person who performed the alignment

Table 5 Data stored in ChIP-seq Metadata collection

To conclude, the database contains three different collections:

The first collection, geneCounts, contains the RNA-sequencing meta data and gene count tables. The results of the differential analysis performed between two gene count tables and the related meta data are stored in the collection named differentialAnalysis. The third collection, ChIPSeq stores the data from ChIP-sequencing and the peak counts.

This adapted, MongoDB supported schema with less collections allows much easier querying (as querying between different collections are difficult and require many steps, while within one collection it is fast and easy) as a result of all the related data being stored together.

Figure showing the final database schema (you could also adapt the power point slide I sent you (see Figure 12 below)).

Figure 10 The relationship between the documents that are stored in collections

Atlas

In this project Atlas cluster was used for hosting the database. Atlas is a cloud database service that allows users to create and store data in a MongoDB database hosted in the cloud. The amount of storage and functionality available is determined by the price plan selected.

The 512 MB of storage provided by the free tier version of MongoDB was sufficient for the current needs of this project. Atlas has a graphical user interface, which is useful to view documents and collections and provides some functions, such as creating or removing databases and collections, performing basic searches within the database, and manually modifying the documents. Furthermore, it allows sharing and collaboration, which makes team working easier. In this project, Atlas was used to share the database with supervisors. Some querying functionality (i.e., projection or the stages of aggregation pipelines) is limited in the free tier version of Atlas, and to overcome this barrier the database was exported from Atlas using the MondoDB dump command and was installed on the local computer. This allowed the final queries to be performed.

1. Writing data to the database

Initially data was imported into the database using the Mongoimport function, which is one of the standard MongoDB command line tools. Mongoimport only allows single document imported each time the command is run. Further to this, it requires that the import data is formatted in JSON format. Importing data in the database using the standard command line tools was found to be slow, tedious, and is prone to user error. It was also difficult to use it for more complex importing functions, such as using keys for identifying the target document of the new file or creating arrays and objects in the existing documents.

After investigating different methods of importing data into MongoDB, it was realised that a programmatic based solution was required. Programmatic database access allows scripts to in a programming language which can read and format data before appending it to the database. There are many different languages, such as Python, C, C# and Perl, which have libraries and methods to connect to MongoDB. For this project it was decided to use JavaScript and the NodeJS runtime environment to connect with our database. It allows fast and convenient, automatised interaction with the database and in addition will allow building a web-based user interface in the future.

JavaScript is a just-in-time compiled, high-level programming language that is along with CSS and HTML, one of the core technologies of the World Wide Web. To run the code on users' devices, all major web browsers have a dedicated JavaScript engine (74). It supports event-

driven, imperative, and functional programming styles, has prototype-based object-orientation, dynamic typing, and first-class functions. Due to its application programming interfaces (APIs) it is suitable for working with text, regular expressions, dates, standard data structures and the Document Object Model (DOM). Originally, JavaScript engines were used exclusively in web browsers, but they became the core components of many applications and servers. Node.js is the most popular runtime system for this server-side scripting.

Node.js is a cross-platform, open-source, back-end JavaScript runtime environment, which uses the V8 engine and runs JavaScript codes outside a web browser. This allows developers to write command line tools and running scripts server-side to create dynamic web content before the page is sent to the user's web browser. Node.js has the ability to effectively work with noSQL databases, such as MongoDB. Node.js is one of the most popular and fast server-side programming tools, while MongoDB is a revolutionary technology for database uses and both employ JavaScript and JSON, thus their combination provides faster and more convenient interactions with the data stored in the database.

MongoDB can be connected to Node.js after installing the Node Package Manager and some packages required by MongoDB. The following link provides a step-by-step guide for the installation and to connect the database: <https://www.npmjs.com/package/mongodb>. Although MongoDB supports other languages, using JavaScript and Node.js allows the further development of the project – the database easily can be connected to a web based front-end, – and nearly all webpage user interfaces are written in JavaScript. NodeJS scripts were written to automate the import of data from csv file into the database. In total 2 scripts were written to write data to the RNASeq gene counts collection, 2 to write data to the RNASeq differential analysis collection and 3 to write data to the ChIP-seq peaks collection. A description of the scripts and the command line arguments required to run them are shown in table 2. Separate flow diagrams showing the operations of each script are shown in Figures 4-8.

Script Name	Function	Command line arguments	Example	Writing location
importBam.js	Writes BAM details into the geneCounts collection.	Name of the BAM file	node importBam.js bamFiles.txt	RNASeq.geneCounts.bamDetails
importFastq.js	Writes FASTQ details into the geneCounts collection.	Name of the FASTQ file	node importFastq.js fastqFiles.txt	RNASeq.geneCounts.bamDetails.fastqDetails
writeGeneCountDocumentToRNASeqData.js	Adds the gene count tables into the geneCounts collection.	Full path to the gene count table files, the name of the file, the ID of the document where it will be added to.	node writeGeneCountDocumentToRNASeqData.js rnaseq/custom_import/files_to_import/gene_counts_data A_41_ReadsPerGene.out.tab counts_1	RNASeq.geneCounts1
writeDiffAnalysis.js	Adds the results of the differential analysis results to the differentialAnalysis collection.	Full path to the differential analysis files, the name of the file, the ID of the document where it will be added to.	node writeDiffAnalysis.js rnaseq/custom_import/files_to_import/differential_analysis_data Bet1VsDMSO_4hr_DownReg.csv DA_3	RNASeq.differentialAnalysis.analysis1
importBamChIP.js	Writes BAM details into the ChIPSeq collection.	Name of the BAM file	node importBamChIP.js chipBAM.txt	RNASeq.ChIPSeq.bamDetails

importFastqChIP.js	Writes BAM details into the ChIPSeq collection.	Name of the FASTQfile	node importFastqChIP.js chipFastq.txt	RNASeq.ChIPSeq. bamDetails.fastqDetails
writePeaksDocumentToChipSeqData.js	Adds the peak count tables into the ChIPSeq collection.	Full path to the peak count files, the name of the file, the ID of the document where it will be added to.	node writePeaksDocuments rnaseq/custom_import/files_to_import/chip_seq 1_PCOS_AR_i7_filtered_trim_bowtie 2UPBlkLstRm_MACS_peaks.out.tab 1	RNASeq.ChIPSeq. peaks1

Table 6 Scripts for writing data to database

Users can run these scripts to append new datasets to the database. Furthermore, it would be simple to incorporate these scripts to run as the backend component of a webpage which allows non-specialist users to append data to the database. During import of data several problems were identified and had to be overcome, such as difficulties in querying due to inappropriate field names or limitations of the size of each document.

In the original RNA-seq gene count tables, the ENSG gene IDs contained a dot character (i.e.: ENSG00000268020.3). The gene IDs were used as field names and as queries could possibly target these IDs of the genes, however, as mentioned above (part mongoDB), the dot characters in MongoDB queries are used for accessing the embedded and nested documents. Therefore, to allow querying using the gene IDs, the writeGeneCountDocumentToRNASeqData.js script (see in Appendix), removed the dots and the following characters in the gene IDs before adding them into the collection – the process is shown on Figure 16. The character after the dot refers to the annotation version of the gene and is implicit to the genome build and not required to identify the gene or for further analysis.

For the ChIP-seq data some of the peak files were between 5-12 MB, while the maximum size of a MongoDB document is 16 MB. Storing the peak files together with their meta data would overcome the 16 MB limitation but storing them independently in different collections would make querying extremely difficult. Therefore, these files could not be imported to the database in their original format. To overcome this challenge, the writePeaksDocumentToChipSeqData.js script (see in Appendix), only considers the first four columns of the file, which include the number of the chromosome, the start and the end of the peak and the MACS ID, as it is shown on Figure 18.

The following diagrams represent the working process of the Node.js scripts from Table 2.

Figure 11 Flow diagram of the process of importBam.js and importBamChIP.js scripts. These scripts write BAM file metadata into the geneCounts and ChIPSeq collections of database RNASEq, respectively.

Figure 12 Flow diagram of the process of `importFastq.js` and `importFastqChIP.js` scripts. These scripts write FASTQ files metadata into the `bamDetails` fields of `geneCounts/ChIPSeq` collections of database RNASeq, respectively.

Figure 13 Flow diagram showing the working process of writeGeneCountDocumentToRNASeqData.js script. The script writes gene count table files into the counts1 field of the geneCounts collection of RNASeq database.

Figure 14 Flow diagram of the process of writeDiffAnalysis.js script. The script writes differential analysis files into the analysis1 field of the differentialAnalysis collection of database RNASeq.

Figure 8 Flow diagram showing the working process of writePeaksDocumentToChIPSeqData.js script. The script writes peak files into the peakCounts field of the ChIPSeq collection of the RNASeq database.

2. Querying the data base

NGS (next-generation sequencing) techniques create massive volumes of DNA/RNA sequences, which require users to access and analyze, however, comparing such large datasets would be time-consuming. The database allows storing of the main results from these large datasets in an organised way by keeping all related data together and thus makes quick and easy comparisons between datasets possible. This database makes easy finding the data stored about different samples and experiments, provides quick access to gene count tables, which can be easily downloaded and to be used for further differential analysis. The user of the database can get information of what data is stored in the database.

Using data from RNA-seq allows comparing gene expressions between different sample pairs, such as healthy or diseased cells and between different disease subtypes and between different treatments. By understanding which genes are over/under expressed in different subtypes of cancers, they could be used as drug targets and thus a cancer-subtype specific treatment can be developed. Using ChIP-seq peak data makes it possible to compare changes in the epigenetic landscape between different samples. This could lead to a better understanding of epigenetic reprogramming of cancer and thus leading to improved diagnostic and treatment options.

Users of this database can access information they would need to form hypothesis, answer a research question, or make a medical decision. By investigating the relationship between the results of different experiments and specific genes, a more personalised medical approach made possible, leading to better treatment outcomes and more positive prognosis. This database can be adapted to another research areas and using it can speed up the process of drug discovery while making it possible to investigate the effects of the drug in a genetic level.

In the next section some queries will provide examples for how the database is used in practice.

Basic queries

A query is a request for data or information from a database. The data will be created as a result of the MQL findings. Queries allow for rapid and thorough inspection of datasets to obtain the data stored in them.

Six basic queries have been developed to allow users to query the information contained in the database and return the data they require:

1. List the number of RNA-seq samples in the database for each sample type
2. List the number of RNA-seq samples in the database for a particular treatment or sample
3. Return the metadata for RNA-seq samples in the database for a particular treatment or sample
4. Search for differential analysis (DA) to find if a comparison between two different samples is contained in the database
5. If the DA for two samples exists in the database, then return the DA results
6. If DA for two samples does not exist, then return the gene counts tables required to perform the differential analysis

These queries will allow users to which RNA-seq datasets are contained in the database and return relevant results. These queries could be run in the background of a search tool in a web application. Details of each query are outlined below.

Basic query details

1. Query 1 is a basic query which will allow the users to see what RNA-sequencing data is available in the database to see if the samples they are interested in are present. This is a basic operation required by all databases. Figure 9 illustrates the logic of the query.

Figure 9 The process of Query 1 - Finds and counts how many different samples are stored in the geneCounts collection
 Figure 15 The process of Query 4b - Finds if the requested gene count tables have been used as a sample or control in the existing differential analysis files in the differentialAnalysis collection

In this case, after querying what samples are available and how many documents contain each sample type, the result is the following:

```

{ "_id" : "Mucinous OC tissue", "count" : 4 }
{ "_id" : "OVCAR cell line", "count" : 12 }
{ "_id" : "Clearcell OC tissue", "count" : 10 }
{ "_id" : "HGSC tissue", "count" : 12 }
  
```

The sample types have been used as ID-s during the grouping and the count represents how many documents of them are available. The query shows that the RNA-seq database contains four different sample types, Mucinous OC tissue, OVCAR cell line, Clearcell OC tissue and HGSC tissue, with 4, 12 ,10 and 12 samples for each respectively.

2. Query 2 looks for more specific information where a user can ask if a particular dataset is available in the database and the number of samples.

In this case the field “treatments” and “sample” both have been used as IDs for grouping the results (figure 10) and then the count represents the sum of the numbers of available sample types with the specified treatment.

Figure 10 The process of Query 2 - Finds and counts how many different treatments are available per sample stored in the geneCounts collection

The results show each treatment for a different sample type separately:

```

{ "_id" : { "treatments" : "None", "sample" : "Mucinous OC tissue" }, "count" : 4
}
{ "_id" : { "treatments" : "BETi 2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line" }, "count" : 4 }
{ "_id" : { "treatments" : "None", "sample" : "HGSC tissue" }, "count" : 12 }
{ "_id" : { "treatments" : "DMSO", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line" }, "count" : 4 }
{ "_id" : { "treatments" : "BETi 1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line" }, "count" : 4 }
{ "_id" : { "treatments" : "None", "sample" : "Clearcell OC tissue" }, "count" : 10
}
  
```

The query shows that the RNA-seq database contains six different treatment-sample combinations: Mucinous OC tissue, HGSC tissue and Clearcell tissue samples did not receive any treatments for 4, 12 and 10 samples respectively. OVCAR cell line has been treated with BETi 2, DMSO and BETi 1 for 4 samples each.

- Query 3 returns requested data from a collection from the documents that match with the arguments stated in the query. In this example the type of the sample and treatment

have been specified (figure 11) and the id of the document which matches these specifications was requested along with the time of the sample collection.

Figure 11 The process of Query 3 - Finds every document where the sample is OVCAR cell line, and it has been treated with BETi 1 in the geneCounts collection

Although four different lines have been returned in the terminal, there are only two different documents which contain these data: counts_1 and counts_2:

```

{ "_id" : "counts_1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",
  "other" : "Collected 4 hrs after treatment" }
{ "_id" : "counts_1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",
  "other" : "Collected 4 hrs after treatment" }
{ "_id" : "counts_2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",
  "other" : "Collected 4 hrs after treatment" }
{ "_id" : "counts_2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",
  "other" : "Collected 4 hrs after treatment" }
  
```

The query shows that the RNA-seq database contains two different documents (counts_1 and counts_2) that store data of OVCAR samples which have been treated with BETi 1 and all of them had been collected 4 hours after the treatment.

The duplication is caused by the two different fastq files related to each document and could be prevented by using the \$group command. However, without grouping the results, more information from the fastq files can be accessed without modifying the structure of the query:

If instead of the time of the collection, the required information is the name of the replicate files, it can be easily changed, and the result will be the following:

```
{ "_id" : "counts_1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",  
  "replicates" : "A42_1.fastq.gz"}  
{ "_id" : "counts_1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",  
  "replicates" : "A42_2.fastq.gz"}  
{ "_id" : "counts_2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",  
  "replicates" : "A41_1.fastq.gz"}  
{ "_id" : "counts_2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1",  
  "replicates" : "A41_2.fastq.gz"}
```

After this modification the query shows that the RNA-seq database contains two different documents (counts_1 and counts_2) that store data of OVCAR samples which have been treated with BETi 1 and the names of the fastq file replicates.

4. If the user wants to find out whether a differential analysis exists in the database between two specified sample, query 4 can answer this question by filtering the differential analysis collection. Query 4 gives different results dependent on whether a) one or more differential analysis between the samples are contained within the database, or b) no differential analysis results are contained within the database for these samples.
 - a. The first step to identify which documents contain the requested samples (figure 12)

Figure 12 The process of Query 4a - Finds every document where the sample is OVCAR cell line, and it has been treated with BETi 1 or DMSO in the geneCounts collection

In this case all documents were requested which contain data of those OVCAR cell line samples which received treatment of BETi 1, BETi 2 or DMSO:

```

{ "_id" : "counts_3", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "DMSO" }
{ "_id" : "counts_3", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "DMSO" }
{ "_id" : "counts_1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1" }
{ "_id" : "counts_1", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1" }
{ "_id" : "counts_9", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 2" }
{ "_id" : "counts_9", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 2" }
{ "_id" : "counts_10", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 2" }
{ "_id" : "counts_10", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 2" }
{ "_id" : "counts_4", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "DMSO" }
{ "_id" : "counts_4", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "DMSO" }
{ "_id" : "counts_2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1" }
{ "_id" : "counts_2", "sample" : "OVCAR cell line", "treatments" : "BETi 1" }
  
```

The query shows that the RNA-seq database contains 12 different documents to store the data of OVCAR samples treated differently: counts_2 and counts_4 store data of samples treated with DMSO, count_1 and count_2 store data of samples treated with BETi 1 and the data of OVCAR cell line treated with BETi 2 can be found in counts_9 and counts_10.

Again, the duplication occurs as a result of the two different fastq files in each document. In case some other fastq details would be requested the query do not have to be modified, just its arguments, as it does not use the \$group command. According to the results, the document with

the ids counts_1, counts_2, counts_3 and counts_4 contain the requested information and thus these documents should be looked for in the differential analysis collection. For the following step the _id values of the documents are required – the previous query returned these.

- b. The next query investigates whether the count tables are present in the GeneCountsSample and in the GeneCountsControl fields of the differential analysis collection (figure 13)

Figure 13 **The process of Query 4b** - Investigates whether the requested gene count tables are present as a sample or a control in the existing differential analysis documents of the differentialAnalysis collection

The query investigated whether counts_1 has been used as a sample or as a control with counts_3 as a sample or a control. The terminal only returns the ID of the document in the differential analysis collection which matches the criterium above:

```

{ "_id" : "DA_5" }
{ "_id" : "DA_3" }
{ "_id" : "DA_1" }
  
```

The result for counts_2 and counts_4 is the same:

```

{ "_id" : "DA_5" }
{ "_id" : "DA_3" }
  
```

```
{ "_id" : "DA_1" }
```

Therefore, the query shows that the data of the differential analysis between OVCAR cell line treated with BETi 1 and DMSO are stored in the documents DA_1, DA_3 and DA_5.

5. In Query 4, the database returned the ID-s of the documents. Using these IDs, users can run another query to investigate the data of the differential analysis. To access the data stored in the documents, simple query can return all the requested information (figure 14)

Figure 14 The process of Query 5 - Displays all the information of the requested document of the differentialAnalysis collection

The query can return the data in interest by adding/removing fields to the \$project command. In this case, only the actual results were required, the meta data was not:

```
{
  "_id" : "DA_1",
  "analysis1" : {
    "ENSG00000228794" : {
      "GeneSymbol" : "LINC01128",
      "baseMean" : "905.050023310131",
      "log2FoldChange" : "1.4546272597632",
      "lfcSE" : "0.216859316849583",
      "stat" : "6.70770009283093",
      "pvalue" : "1.97715750730287e-11",
      "padj" : "4.06156545491369e-10",
      "biotype" : "processed_transcript",
      "abslog2FoldChange" : "1.4546272597632"
    },
    "ENSG00000187608" : {
```

```

"GeneSymbol" : "ISG15",
"baseMean" : "1233.33088831714",
"log2FoldChange" : "0.706995719663866",
"lfcSE" : "0.248606215898894",
"stat" : "2.84383766153053",
"pvalue" : "0.00445737518892324",
"padj" : "0.0173092568820379",
"biotype" : "protein_coding",
"abslog2FoldChange" : "0.706995719663866"
},

```

...

Therefore, the query shows that the data of document DA_1 of the differential analysis collection between OVCAR cell line treated with BETi 1 and DMSO.

In case, only a specific gene is in interest, the terminal will only return the information related to it within the queried differential analysis document, after using another query (figure 15):

Figure 15 **The process of Query 5** - Finds and displays the data of the analysis1 field related to the requested gene in the differentialAnalysis collection

In this query the specified gene was the LINC01128 gene:

```

{
  "_id" : "DA_1",
  "info" : {
    "ENSG00000228794" : {
      "GeneSymbol" : "LINC01128",
      "baseMean" : "905.050023310131",

```

```

    "log2FoldChange" : "1.4546272597632",
    "lfcSE" : "0.216859316849583",
    "stat" : "6.70770009283093",
    "pvalue" : "1.97715750730287e-11",
    "padj" : "4.06156545491369e-10",
    "biotype" : "processed_transcript",
    "abslog2FoldChange" : "1.4546272597632"
  }
}
}

```

The query shows the document of the differential analysis collection which contains the LINC01128 gene.

6. If there is no differential analysis in the collection between the specified gene count tables, but the relevant samples are present in the database, Query 6 returns the gene count tables allowing the differential analysis can be performed outside of the database. However, more steps required to download the required tables to the user's computer. Once the differential analysis has been performed, users can then use the upload scripts to append the new differential analysis results (see previous section).

- a. The first query creates a new collection with the results (figure 16)

Figure 16 The process of Query 6 - Finds the requested document of the geneCounts collection and writes its data into a new collection

- b. The new collection can be downloaded in JSON or CSV format to the user's computer by using the mongoexport command.

2. Worked examples of using the database for research

To demonstrate the efficacy of the database two worked examples of database usage have been performed. The first example compares gene expression of HGSOC cell line in an untreated sample and a sample treated with a BET inhibitor compound. The second example, compares the gene expression of HGSOC with clear cell ovarian cancer samples. Having obtained the top ten up and down-regulated genes, we queried the ChIP-seq collection to identify H3K27ac peaks within the gene promoter regions. This allows us to relate gene expression to modifications of the underlying epigenetic landscape in different ovarian cancer subtypes.

Example 1 – compare RNA expression in HGSC ovarian cancer and clear-cell ovarian cancer untreated vs the presence of a drug (BET inhibitor)

In this example the differential analysis is present in the database (DA_5 and DA_6). By using the RNA-seq data, differences in gene expression between cancer subtypes can be detected. Figure 17 shows the process of sortDiffAn.js, the script which can find the top ten dysregulated genes (shown in Figure 18) in documents DA_5 and DA_6, which store data of differential analysis performed between untreated ovarian cancer versus in the presence of BETi 2 or BETi 1 drugs, respectively– the top ten upregulated are associated with HGSC subtype, while the top ten downregulated are in relation with clear-cell carcinoma. These results can be confirmed by looking at specific genes, such as gene CCR1 (C chemokine receptor type 1) which is linked to tumor invasion and metastatic progression (75) and found to be overly expressed in endometrioid carcinoma and clear-cell ovarian cancer (75). Furthermore, it plays an important role in the development of resistance against platinum-based chemotherapy agents (75). Thus, finding these dysregulated genes can lead to better understanding of the drug mechanism of action used to treat the different subtyped of cancer. These dysregulated genes could be targeted by subtype specific drugs. To further investigate the effects of these genes on cancer phenotypes, assays, such as siRNA can be designed.

Figure 17 The process of sortDiffAn.js -The script first finds the matching document to the provided argument, open the analysis.1 field of the document, calculates the pAdj values, sort out the ones which are not < 0.05, sorts the results by the value of log2FoldChange fields and displays the top 10 highest or lowest according to the arguments: ascending/descending.

DA_6	Downregulated	Upregulated
BET1 vs DMSO	ENSG00000163823 CCR1	ENSG00000266709 RP11-21401.2
	ENSG00000106006 HOXA6	ENSG00000125462 C1orf61
	ENSG00000270021 CTC-203F4.2	ENSG00000176840 MIR7-3HG
	ENSG00000177468 OLIG3	ENSG00000178404 CEP295NL
	ENSG00000144227 NXPH2	ENSG00000180730 SHISA2
	ENSG00000270002 RP11-93H12.4	ENSG00000125430 HS3ST3B1
	ENSG00000197619 ZNF615	ENSG00000225611 RP11-70C1.1
	ENSG00000259727 RP11-1069G10.2	ENSG00000005513 SOX8
	ENSG00000211786 TRAV8-2	ENSG00000276216 CH17-373J23.1
	ENSG00000136866 ZFP37	ENSG00000281491 DNAJB5-AS1

DA_5	Downregulated	Upregulated
BET2 vs DMSO	ENSG00000163823 CCR1	ENSG00000266709 RP11-21401.2
	ENSG00000259727 RP11-1069G10.2	ENSG00000125430 HS3ST3B1
	ENSG00000247746 USP51	ENSG00000005513 SOX8
	ENSG00000144227 NXPH2	ENSG00000180730 SHISA2
	ENSG00000211786 TRAV8-2	ENSG00000176840 MIR7-3HG
	ENSG00000128342 LIF	ENSG00000131459 GFPT2
	ENSG00000268812 RP1-102K2.8	ENSG00000182759 MAFA
	ENSG00000168685 IL7R	ENSG00000136099 PCDH8
	ENSG00000115165 CYTIP	ENSG00000163273 NPPC
	ENSG00000272043 RP11-44N11.3	ENSG00000273199 AP000692.10

Figure 116 The top 10 downregulated and upregulated genes in RNA-seq, comparing different BETi treatments with DMSO. The same genes are indicated by the same colours.

Example 2 – identify dysregulation of genes in HGSC vs clear cell ovarian cancer in RNA-seq then look for relevant modifications to histone marks (from ChIP-seq).

In this example the differential analysis was not present in the database. First, the gene count tables had to be accessed (Query 6a) then a differential analysis has been performed. The result of the analysis then has been uploaded to the database using writeDiffAnalysis.js. By using the RNA-seq data the differences between cancer phenotypes between subtypes can be understood better. Using the sortDiffAn.js script, the top ten upregulated and downregulated genes could be determined:

Top ten downregulated genes:

'ENSG00000198914'	SYMBOL: 'POU3F3'
'ENSG00000075043'	SYMBOL: 'KCNQ2'
'ENSG00000043355'	SYMBOL: 'ZIC2'
'ENSG00000101210'	SYMBOL: 'EEF1A2'
'ENSG00000260676'	SYMBOL: 'LINC01541'
'ENSG00000178772'	SYMBOL: 'CPN2'
'ENSG00000198535'	SYMBOL: 'C2CD4A'
'ENSG00000163530'	SYMBOL: 'DPPA2'
'ENSG00000129988'	SYMBOL: 'LBP'
'ENSG00000167798'	SYMBOL: 'C3P1'

Top ten upregulated genes:

'ENSG00000163331'	SYMBOL: 'DAPL1'
'ENSG00000236253'	SYMBOL: 'SLC25A3P1'
'ENSG00000278408'	SYMBOL: 'RP11-112318.1'
'ENSG00000205835'	SYMBOL: 'GMNC'
'ENSG00000095713'	SYMBOL: 'CRTAC1'
'ENSG00000162951'	SYMBOL: 'LRRTM1'
'ENSG00000271399'	SYMBOL: 'RP4-799G3.2'
'ENSG00000187715'	SYMBOL: 'KBTBD12'
'ENSG00000169248'	SYMBOL: 'CXCL11'
'ENSG00000183036'	SYMBOL: 'PCP4'

Seeing the genes that are differently expressed between subtypes give an indication of what genes should be targeted by subtype specific drugs leading to the development of precision

medicine. By mapping epigenetic modifications, such as H3K27ac levels in gene promoters, the development of differences between cancer subtypes can be understood better. Finding those epigenetic mechanisms which are responsible for differential gene expressions between subtypes could lead to better diagnostics and improved treatment selection.

<https://www.ensembl.org> has been used to find the promoter regions of these dysregulated genes. Once the promoter regions have found, findPeaks.js script (figure 19) has been used to filter ChIP-seq data to see if the dysregulation is caused by changes to the H3k27ac signal in the gene promoter regions. The following table shows the genes, their location at chromosome, their peak region, the ID of the document which contains the peaks within the range and the MACS_peak ID.

Figure 19 **The process of findPeaks.js** - The script reads the opens the peakCalls field of every document in the ChIPSeq collection, filters those where the peak callers are between the ranges of the ones in the arguments and if the chromosome matches to the one given in the arguments – then displays the results.

	gene ID	symbol	chromosome	range low	range high	doc ID	MACS peak
D O W N R E G U L A T E D	ENSG00000198914	POU3F3	chr 2	104,842,200	104,867,401	2	MACS_peak_3662,MACS_peak_3663,MACS_peak_3664,MACS_peak_3665,MACS_peak_3666
						3	MACS_peak_8595,MACS_peak_8596
	ENSG00000075043	KCNQ2	chr 20	63,453,341	63,454,542		no result
						2	MACS_peak_1945,MACS_peak_1946,MACS_peak_1947,MACS_peak_1948,MACS_peak_1949,MACS_peak_1950,MACS_peak_1951,MACS_peak_1952,MACS_peak_1953,MACS_peak_1954,MACS_peak_1955,MACS_peak_1956,MACS_peak_1957,MACS_peak_1958
	ENSG00000043355	ZIC2	chr 13	99,978,200	99,988,401	3	MACS_peak_4021,MACS_peak_4022,MACS_peak_4023,MACS_peak_4024,MACS_peak_4025,MACS_peak_4026,MACS_peak_4027,MACS_peak_4028,MACS_peak_4029,MACS_peak_4030,MACS_peak_4031,MACS_peak_4032
						10	no MACS_peak, 5 results
	ENSG00000101210	EEF1A2	chr 20	63,496,200	63,499,801		no result
	ENSG00000260676	LINC01541	chr 13	-	-		
	ENSG00000178772	CPN2	chr 3	-	-		
	ENSG00000198535	C2CD4A	chr 15	62,066,400	62,069,401	10	no MACS_peak (62068180 - 62068615)
ENSG00000163530	DPPA2	chr 3	109,315,801	109,316,601	10	no MACS_peak (109315922 - 109316324)	
ENSG00000129988	LBP	chr 20	-	-			
ENSG00000167798	C3P1	chr 19	-	-			
U P R E G U L A T E D	ENSG00000163331	DAPL1	chr 2	158,794,941	158,795,542		no result
	ENSG00000236253	SLC25A3P1	chr 1	53,415,158	53,415,959		no result
	ENSG00000278408	RP11-112318.1	chr 15	71,547,000	71,547,201		no result
	ENSG00000205835	GMINC	chr 3	190,862,200	190,863,801	10	no MACS_peak (190862885 - 190863089)
	ENSG00000095713	CRTAC1	chr 10	98,029,800	98,031,401	3	MACS_peak_2101
	ENSG00000162951	LRRTM1	chr 2	80,303,600	80,304,801		no result
	ENSG00000271399	RP4-799G3.2	chr 1	-	-		
	ENSG00000187715	KBTD12	chr 3	127,914,601	127,917,001		no result
	ENSG00000169248	CXCL11	chr 4	76,023,600	76,023,801		no result
	ENSG00000183036	PCP4	chr 21	99,867,600	99,868,600		no result

Table 7 *The top ten upregulated and downregulated genes with their related location at chromosome, their peak region, the ID of the document which contains the peaks within the range and the MACS_peak ID*

Using this information can lead to more specific drug development to the different phenotypes of cancers and the development of personalized medicine.

The H3K27ac is predominately an enhancer mark, and that it would be simple to use the script to investigate differences in enhancers relating to the gene.

5. Discussion

Large amounts of NGS data will be analyzed to discover gene expression and regulatory patterns in human disease genomes.

Expression and regulatory peaks for many marks in a large number of samples must be compared.

RNAseq can discriminate samples based on functional expression pattern, identifying regulatory markers in the form of transient ChiP seq files – from epigenetic enzymes – allow for the identification of targeted regulatory frameworks.

While the basic structure of the genome lends itself to comprehending this complicated interplay, viewing at the 3D scale of the genome is complex. A database that is compatible with simple queries from researchers and/or doctors may aid in the identification of new and unique patterns in data, which then speaks to visualisation tactics to bring epigenetic modifications of the genome to light.

A database was needed which can store and organise large datasets originate from new generation sequencing. MongoDB has been recognised as a potential database for this purpose as it has high flexibility, thus storing quickly changing datasets is possible. It has its own querying language, the MongoDB Query Language, which allows quick and easy interaction with the database. It is also accessible by using Node.js and it supports JavaScript therefore these could be used not only for the back-end, but also for further, front-end development. Such as designing a web-based user interface. Creating a graphical user interface will allow interaction and access with the data stored in the database without requiring the user to write queries or scripts. Interactions, such as uploading more data, downloading data, modifying data or creating new fields could be done by using simple action buttons, while queries which are used to find the requested information could be run in the background by performing an advanced search on the interface. The above-mentioned field name limitation could be easily done by creating a drop-down list with the existing field name or adding an error message if the new field name given by the user contains characters in the already existing field names. This interface would make the database more accessible to researchers and medical practitioners who are not familiar with query or coding languages but could also be available for the public. While it would help researchers to form new hypothesis and answer research

questions, medical practitioners could use it to quickly find the most suitable treatment option for the subtype of cancer their patient is suffering from.

Basic queries were design the test the functions of the database and to answer biological questions. The database makes possible the comparison of large datasets from many different sources, including publicly available datasets. This function highly increases the speed of answering research questions and can expand research to a wider area. As MongoDB provides a central repository of data, data from existing databases can be combined so it is easy to share with a team that may analyse, or update the data as needed. It is typically used to consolidate data from many sources. Once done, the saved data may be readily organized, accessed, analysed, enhanced, and secured.

The database can be updated to store new types of data including single cell RNA-seq. New fields can be added easily to the geneCounts collection of the RNA-seq database to store information about cell types in the samples and the numbers of cells of each sample. Single cell RNA-sequencing allows separation of different cell types i.e.: immune cells, within RNA-seq samples. Therefore, the gene expressions of different cells within a sample could be determined which would improve further to understand the mechanism of cells in a tumour microenvironment.

By enforcing the use of certain fields and limiting on the values fields can take within the database using the json schema, duplication caused errors can be avoided. For example, there will only be certain sample names (i.e., HGSC cell line, clear cell tissue) to make sure that users will not assign names with different spelling to refer to the same sample (i.e., HGSC cell line vs High grade serous OC cell line), as this would make searching difficult. If the datatype for the field is not present, users would be able to add these the datatype to the schema.

Other forms of NGS data including ATAC-seq and whole genome sequencing could be added to the database, as they would follow a similar schema to RNA-seq and ChIP-seq. ATAC-Seq is an abbreviation that stands for Assay for Transposase-Accessible Chromatin with High-Throughput Sequencing. The ATAC-Seq approach is based on the creation of next-generation sequencing (NGS) libraries with the hyperactive transposase Tn5. NGS adapters are loaded onto the transposase, allowing for chromatin disruption and integration into open chromatin

areas at the same time. The resulting library may be sequenced using NGS, and the sections of the genome with open or accessible chromatin are evaluated using bioinformatics. Whole genome sequencing (WGS) is a service that gives full coverage of an individual's whole genome at once. WGS may be used to provide a high-resolution, base-by-base image of the genome, catch both big and small variations that would otherwise go undetected, and identify probable causal variants for future research of gene expression and regulatory mechanisms.

Genomic data visualization is critical for interpretation and hypothesis formulation, as well as a useful tool for presenting findings. The discovery of unanticipated patterns and the formulation of hypotheses in huge volumes of genomic and other linked data is a significant problem in data-driven research. If MongoDB has a built in function, Charts, and discovering its abilities could be a focus for a further study.

The ability of the database to get expanded and its flexible schema allow storing different datasets of different cell types allow further comparison and using advanced queries and automatized scripts, visualisation tools etc. hidden patterns of gene expressions in different diseases could be discovered. By identifying gene expressions which are responsible for the manifestation of a subtype of a disease, prevention could be improved to by performing genetic analysis as part of the screening process and if the genes are present preventative treatment could be started.

Functional genomics and ability to inform clinical decisions by identifying different subtypes of a disease and investigate which treatment each subtype reacts the best. Clinicians would have access to the database and when they are in the position to decide on a treatment for a patient, they can make their decision based on the genetic profile of their patients. This personalised approach could lead to more effective treatments, faster recovery from disease, longer survival with potentially less side effect, reduction in the rate of relapses and reduced health care costs.

Cancer features can be influenced by epigenetic regulation. Because it is probable to change epigenetic genes, they might be considered of as possible cancer therapeutic targets. By examining what are the top genes expressed by a cell and comparing these results to different treatments and combinations of treatments, the most effective treatment combination could be chosen for every patient based on their genetic profile.

5. Conclusion

The hypothesis “**Developing a flexible database method is crucial in understanding the integration of transcriptomic and epigenomic data (mainly derived from ChIP seq), helping to derive scientific hypothesis and analysis of large NGS datasets toward new disease related target ID in HGSOC**” has been tested and proven to be right: **a flexible database has been tested to use for NGS,**

The efficacy of the database has been proven by the queries and the querying scripts. Further development of the database and the scripts and the development of a graphic user interface would expand the potential of the database.

The database could be used as a basis for further development of a wider, more complex database that could help in identifying patterns.

Appendix

```
1.importBam.js
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);

const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

var bamObjects = [];
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
    .createReadStream('./files_to_import/meta_data/' + fileToImport)
    .pipe(parse({
      delimiter: ["\t"]
    }));
  var headers;
  var headersSaved = false;
  var j = 0;
  for await (const record of parser) {
    if (!headersSaved) { headers = record; headersSaved = true; continue; }
    bamObjects[j] = {};
    for (var i = 0; i < record.length; i++) {
      bamObjects[j][headers[i]] = record[i];
    }
    j++;
  }
}

async function run() {
  try {
    await client.connect();

    const database = client.db("RNASeq");
    const geneCounts = database.collection("geneCounts2");
    console.info(bamObjects.length);
    for (var bam of bamObjects) {
      const filter = { bamFiles: bam.id };
      // this option instructs the method to create a document if no documents match the filter
      const options = { upsert: true };
      // create a document that sets the plot of the movie
      const updateDoc = {
        $set: {
          bamDetails: bam
        },
      },
    }
  }
}
```

```
};
const result = await geneCounts.updateMany(filter, updateDoc, options);
console.log(
  `${result.matchedCount} document(s) matched the filter, updated
${result.modifiedCount} document(s)`,
);
}
} finally {
  await client.close();
}
}
```

```
(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }
  await processFile()
  run().catch(console.dir);
})();
```

2. importFastq.js

```
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);

const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

var fastqObjects = [];
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
    .createReadStream('./files_to_import/meta_data/' + fileToImport)
    .pipe(parse({
      delimiter: ["\t"]
    }));
  var headers;
  var headersSaved = false;
  var j = 0;
  for await (const record of parser) {
    if (!headersSaved) { headers = record; headersSaved = true; continue; }
    fastqObjects[j] = {};
    for (var i = 0; i < record.length; i++) {
      fastqObjects[j][headers[i]] = record[i];
    }
    j++;
  }
}

async function run() {
  try {
    await client.connect();

    const database = client.db("RNASeq");
    const geneCounts = database.collection("geneCounts2");
    console.info(fastqObjects.length);
    for (var fastq of fastqObjects) {
      const filter = { $or: [{ 'bamDetails.fastq1': fastq.id }, { 'bamDetails.fastq2': fastq.id }]};
      // this option instructs the method to create a document if no documents match the filter
      const options = { upsert: true };
      // create a document that sets the plot of the movie
      const updateDoc = {
        $push: {
          'bamDetails.fastqDetails': fastq
        },
      };
    }
  }
}
```

```
    const result = await geneCounts.updateMany(filter, updateDoc, options);
    console.log(
      `${result.matchedCount} document(s) matched the filter, updated
    ${result.modifiedCount} document(s)`,
    );
  }
} finally {
  await client.close();
}
}
```

```
(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }
  await processFile()
  run().catch(console.dir);
})();
```

3. writeGeneCount

```
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);
const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

const fastcsv = require("fast-csv")
const ws = fs.createWriteStream("testMongoDBQuery.csv")

// You need to change these parameters
var db = "RNASeq"
var collection = "geneCounts2"

var doc = {};
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
var id = process.argv.slice(2)[1];
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
    .createReadStream(fileToImport)
    .pipe(parse({
      delimiter: ["\t"]
    }));
  var cnt = 0;
  for await (const record of parser) {
    record[0] = record[0].replace(/.\d*/, "");
    doc[record[0]] = []
    for (var i = 0; i < record.length; i++) {
      if (i == 0) {
        continue;
      }
      doc[record[0]].push(record[i])
    }
    cnt = cnt + 1
  }
}

// Update document
async function run2() {
  try {
    await client.connect();
    const database = client.db(db);
    const newGeneCount = database.collection(collection);
    const result = await newGeneCount.findOneAndUpdate({ "_id" : id},
      { $set: { geneCounts1 : doc}});
    console.log(`Gene counts added to document: ${result.value["_id"]}`)
  }
}
```

```

    }
  finally
  {
    await client.close();
  }
}
(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }
  await processFile()
  run2().catch(console.dir);
})()

```

4. writeDifferentialAnalysis.js

```

const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);
const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

const fastcsv = require("fast-csv")

// You need to change these parameters
var db = "RNASeq"
var collection = "differentialAnalysis"

var doc = {};
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
var id = process.argv.slice(2)[1];
var fieldNames;
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
    .createReadStream(fileToImport)
    .pipe(parse({
      delimiter: [","]
    }));
  var cnt = 0;
  for await (const record of parser) {
    if (cnt == 0) { fieldNames = record; }
    else {
      doc[record[0]] = {}
      for (var i = 1; i < record.length; i++) {
        doc[record[0]][fieldNames[i].replace(/\s\d*/, "")] = record[i]
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }
  }
  cnt = cnt + 1
}
}

// Update document
async function run2() {
  try {
    await client.connect();
    const database = client.db(db);
    const differentialAnalysis = database.collection(collection);
    const result = await differentialAnalysis.findOneAndUpdate({ "_id" : id},
    { $set: { analysis1 : doc}});
    console.log(`Analysis added to document: ${result.value["_id"]}`)
  }
  finally
  {
    await client.close();
  }
}

(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }
  await processFile()
  run2().catch(console.dir);
})();

```

5. importBamChIP.j

```

const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);

const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

var bamObjects = [];
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
  .createReadStream('./files_to_import/chip_seq/' + fileToImport)
  .pipe(parse({
    delimiter: ["\t"]
  }));
});

```

```

var headers;
var headersSaved = false;
var j = 0;
for await (const record of parser) {
  if (!headersSaved) { headers = record; headersSaved = true; continue; }
  bamObjects[j] = {};
  for (var i = 0; i < record.length; i++) {
    bamObjects[j][headers[i]] = record[i];
  }
  j++;
}
}

```

```

async function run() {
  try {
    await client.connect();

    const database = client.db("RNASeq");
    const ChIPSeq = database.collection("ChIPSeq");
    console.info(bamObjects.length);
    for (var bam of bamObjects) {
      const filter = { bamFiles: bam.id };
      // this option instructs the method to create a document if no documents match the filter
      const options = { upsert: true };
      // create a document that sets the plot of the movie
      const updateDoc = {
        $set: {
          bamDetails: bam
        },
      };
      const result = await ChIPSeq.updateMany(filter, updateDoc, options);
      console.log(
        `${result.matchedCount} document(s) matched the filter, updated
        ${result.modifiedCount} document(s)`,
      );
    }
  } finally {
    await client.close();
  }
}

```

```

(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }
  await processFile()
  run().catch(console.dir);
})();

```

6. importFastqChIP.js

```
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);

const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

var fastqObjects = [];
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
    .createReadStream('./files_to_import/chip_seq/' + fileToImport)
    .pipe(parse({
      delimiter: ["\t"]
    }));
  var headers;
  var headersSaved = false;
  var j = 0;
  for await (const record of parser) {
    if (!headersSaved) { headers = record; headersSaved = true; continue; }
    fastqObjects[j] = {};
    for (var i = 0; i < record.length; i++) {
      fastqObjects[j][headers[i]] = record[i];
    }
    j++;
  }
}

async function run() {
  try {
    await client.connect();

    const database = client.db("RNASeq");
    const ChIPSeq = database.collection("ChIPSeq");
    console.info(fastqObjects.length);
    for (var fastq of fastqObjects) {
      const filter = { 'bamDetails.fastq': fastq.id };
      // this option instructs the method to create a document if no documents match the filter
      const options = { upsert: true };
      // create a document that sets the plot of the movie
      const updateDoc = {
        $set: {
          'bamDetails.fastqDetails': fastq
        },
      };
    };
  }
}
```

```

    const result = await ChIPSeq.updateMany(filter, updateDoc, options);
    console.log(
      `${result.matchedCount} document(s) matched the filter, updated
    ${result.modifiedCount} document(s)`,
    );
  }
} finally {
  await client.close();
}
}
}

```

```

(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }
  await processFile()
  run().catch(console.dir);
})();

```

```

writePeaksDocumentToChIPSeqData.js
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);
const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

```

```

const fastcsv = require("fast-csv")

```

```

var db = "RNASeq"
var collection = "ChIPSeq"

```

```

var doc = {};
var fileToImport = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
var id = parseInt(process.argv.slice(2)[1], 10)
const processFile = async () => {
  const parser = fs
    .createReadStream(fileToImport)
    .pipe(parse({
      delimiter: ["\t"]
    }));
}

```

```

var cnt = 0;
for await (const record of parser) {
  record[3] = record[3].replace(/./, "")
  doc[record[3]] = []
  for (var i = 0; i < record.length && i < 3; i++) {

```

```

    doc[record[3]].push(record[i])
  }
  cnt = cnt + 1
}
}

async function run2() {
  try {

    await client.connect();
    const database = client.db(db);
    const chipSeq = database.collection(collection);
    const result = await chipSeq.findOneAndUpdate({ "_id" : id},
    { $set: { peakCounts : doc}});
    console.log(`Peak counts added to document: ${result.value["_id"]}`)
  }
  finally
  {
    await client.close();

  }
}

(async () => {
  if (!fileToImport) {
    console.info('provide file name as argument');
    return;
  }

  await processFile()
  run2().catch(console.dir);
})()

```

7. sortDiffAn.js

```
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);
const parse = require('csv-parse');
const fs = require('fs');

const fastcsv = require("fast-csv")

// You need to change these parameters
var db = "RNASeq"
var collection = "differentialAnalysis"

var analysisId = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
var order = process.argv.slice(2)[1];
var result = null
var sortedresult = []
async function run2() {
  try {
    await client.connect();
    const database = client.db(db);
    const differentialAnalysis = database.collection(collection);
    result = await differentialAnalysis.findOne({ "_id" : analysisId});
    result =result.analysis1
  }
  finally
  {
    await client.close();
  }
}

function sortByLog2FoldChange() {

Object.entries(result).forEach(([key, value]) => {
  let calculatedPadj = calculatePadj(value.padj)
  if (calculatedPadj <0.05) {
    sortedresult.push([key, value, calculatedPadj])
  }
})

sortedresult.sort(function(a, b) {
return parseFloat(a[1].log2FoldChange) - parseFloat(b[1].log2FoldChange);
});

if (order === 'descending') {
  sortedresult.reverse()
}
}
```

```
function calculatePadj(padj) {  
  if (padj.match('e')) {  
    let base = padj.split('e')  
    return parseFloat(base[0]) * Math.pow(2.7182818284,parseInt(base[1],10))  
  } else {  
    return parseFloat(padj)  
  }  
}
```

```
(async () => {  
  if (order !== 'ascending' && order !== 'descending') {  
    console.info('specify ascending or descending');  
    return;  
  }  
}
```

```
await run2().catch(console.dir);  
if (!result) {  
  console.info('cannot find document');  
  return;  
}
```

```
sortByLog2FoldChange()  
for (let i = 0; i < 10; i++) {  
  console.log(sortedresult[i])  
}  
})()
```

8. findPeaks.js

```
const { MongoClient } = require("mongodb");
const uri = 'mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-
basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/myFirstDatabase?retryWrites=true&w=majority'
const client = new MongoClient(uri);

// You need to change these parameters
var db = "RNASeq"
var collection = "ChIPSeq"

var rangeLow = process.argv.slice(2)[0];
var rangeHigh = process.argv.slice(2)[1];
var chr = process.argv.slice(2)[2];
var result = null
var matches = []
async function run2() {
  try {
    await client.connect();
    const database = client.db(db);
    const differentialAnalysis = database.collection(collection);
    result = await differentialAnalysis.find({}).toArray();
  }
  finally
  {
    await client.close();
  }
}

function getRangeMatches() {
  for (let document of result) {
    if ("peakCounts" in document) {
      Object.entries(document.peakCounts).forEach(([macsID, macsArray]) => {
        if (macsArray[0] == chr && parseInt(macsArray[1], 10) >= rangeLow &&
            parseInt(macsArray[2], 10) <= rangeHigh) {
          matches.push({
            id: document._id,
            fileName: document.fileName,
            macsID: macsArray
          })
        }
      })
    }
  }
}

(async () => {
  if (isNaN(rangeLow) || isNaN(rangeHigh) || !chr) {
    console.info('specify range and chr');
  }
})
```

```
return;
}
```

```
await run2().catch(console.dir);
getRangeMatches()
console.log(matches)
})()
```

Query 1

```
db.geneCounts.aggregate({$unwind:"$bamDetails"},{$unwind:"$bamDetails.fastqDetails"},
{$group: {_id:"$bamDetails.fastqDetails.sample",count:{$sum:1}}})
```

Query 2

```
db.geneCounts.aggregate({$unwind:"$bamDetails"},{$unwind:"$bamDetails.fastqDetails"},
{$group: {_id:{"treatments":"$bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments","sample":"$bamDetails.fastqDetails.sample"},count:{$sum:1}}})
```

Query 3

```
db.geneCounts2.aggregate({$match: {"bamDetails.fastqDetails.sample": "OVCAR cell line",
"bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments": "BETi
1"}},{$unwind:"$bamDetails"},{$unwind:"$bamDetails.fastqDetails"},{$project: {_id: 1,
"sample":"$bamDetails.fastqDetails.sample",
"treatments":"$bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments",
"other":"$bamDetails.fastqDetails.other"}}})
```

Query 4

Step 1

```
db.geneCounts2.aggregate({$match: {"bamDetails.fastqDetails.sample":"OVCAR cell
line",$or:[{"bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments":"BETi
1"}, {"bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments":"BETi
```

```
2"}, {"bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments": "DMSO"}] }}, {"$unwind: "$bamDetails"}, {"$unwind: "$bamDetails.fastqDetails"}, {"$project: { _id: 1, "sample": "$bamDetails.fastqDetails.sample", "treatments": "$bamDetails.fastqDetails.treatments" } })
```

Step 2

```
db.differentialAnalysis.aggregate( { $match: { $or: [ {"geneCountsSample.0": "counts_2", "geneCountsControl.0": "counts_4"}, {"geneCountsSample.0": "counts_4", "geneCountsControl.0": "counts_2"}, {"geneCountsSample.1": "counts_2", "geneCountsControl.1": "counts_4"}, {"geneCountsSample.1": "counts_4", "geneCountsControl.1": "counts_2"} ] } }, {"$unwind: "$geneCountsSample"}, {"$unwind: "$geneCountsControl"}, {"$project: { _id: 1 } })
```

Query 4b

```
db.differentialAnalysis.aggregate( { $match: { _id: "DA_1" } }, {"$project: { fileName: 0, dysRegulation: 0, geneCountsSample: 0, geneCountsControl: 0, filters: 0 } }).pretty()
```

Query 5

```
db.differentialAnalysis.aggregate( [ { $match: { _id: "DA_1" } }, {"$project: { obj: { $subjectToArray: "$analysis1" } } }, {"$project: { _id: 1, obj: { $filter: { input: "$obj", as: "item", cond: { $eq: [ "$$item.v.GeneSymbol", "LINC01128" ] } } } } }, {"$project: { info: { $arrayToObject: "$obj" } } } ] ).pretty()
```

Query 5b

```
db.geneCounts.aggregate({$match: {_id:"counts_1"}},{$project: {fileName:0, counts: 0, bamFiles:0, method:0, countTableType:0, date:0, operator:0, fileLocations:0, bamDetails:0}}).pretty()
```

Query 6

```
Db.geneCounts.aggregate({ $match: { _id: "counts_1" } }, { $project: { filename: 0, counts: 0, bamFiles: 0, method: 0, countTableType: 0, date: 0, operator: 0, fileLocations: 0, bamDetails: 0 } }, {$out:"result"}).pretty()
```

Query 6B

```
mongoexport --uri="mongodb+srv://m001-student:m001-mongodb-basics@sandbox.m2y4r.mongodb.net/RNASeq" --collection=result --type=json --out=counts3.json --pretty
```

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